

Master Thesis

Design of magnetic interactions in doped topological insulators

Author

Rubel Mozumder

Heinrich-Heine Universität, Düsseldorf

Affiliated with

*Peter Grünberg Institut(PGI-1) and Institute for Advanced
Simulation(IAS-1),
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Jülich*

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Supervisor

Dr. rer. nat. Philipp Rüßmann

Peter Grünberg Institut(PGI-1)
Institute for Advanced Simulation(IAS-1)
Forschungszentrum Jülich

Reviewer 1

Prof. Dr. Stefan Blügel

Peter Grünberg Institut (PGI-1)

Institute for Advanced Simulation (IAS-1)

Forschungszentrum Jülich

Reviewer 2

Prof. Dr. Reinhold Egger

Institut für Theoretische Physik IV

Heinrich-Heine Universität, Düsseldorf

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January 18, 2022

Rubel Mozumder

Table 1: Some abbreviations used in this work

Abbr.	Expansion	Abbr.	Expansion
TI	topological insulator	TIs	topological insulators
QSHE	quantum spin Hall effect	3DTIs	3D topological insulators
QAHI	quantum anomalous Hall insulator	2DTIs	2D topological insulators
QHE	quantum Hall effect	LR	linear regression
TRS	time reversal symmetry	SOC	spin-orbit coupling
DFT	density functional theory	TRIM	time reversal invariant momentum
KKR	Korringa Kohn Rostocker	GF	Green Function
TKNN	Thouless, Kohmoto, Nightingale, and den Nijs	QAH	quantum anomalous Hall
FM	ferromagnetic	AFM	anti-ferromagnetic
ORM	object-relational mapping	DAG	directed acyclic graph
CPA	coherent potential approximation	JuKKR	Jülich KKR
RKKY	Ruderman–Kittel – Kasuya–Yosida	DOS	Density of States
DTR	Decision Tree regression	RMSE	root mean square error
KRR	Kernel Ridge Regression	R ²	R squared

List of Figures

1	Quantum Hall Effect. The skipping orbits on the edges moves diferent direction for electron (towards left) and holes(towards right). The electrons on the bulk region are in the circular motion rather than drift motion responsible for bulk insulating phase. source: [1]	5
2	2D QSHE with Dirac dispersion: (a) Two 1D edge states for spin up and down in opposite directions. (b) Dispersion of two non degenerate spin states. The crossing point or Dirac point, is the meeting point for conduction and valence band. source: [2] . . .	6
3	Schematic of the three topological effects with the year of experimental discoveries in the brackets. The edge states for different spin channels are indicated with different colors. The labels \vec{B} and \vec{M} represent the external magnetic field and internal magnetization due to magnetic doping, respectively [3]	7
4	Two Kramers pairs at the edges from spin-orbit couplings. Each Kramers pairs belongs two Time-Reversal-Invariant-Momentum (TRIM, points of degeneracy of band structure) points at $\vec{k} = \pi, 0$. The points come at the $\vec{k} = -\pi, 0$ due to the periodicity of the Brillouin zone. Therefore TRIMs corresponds to a Kramer pairs at $\vec{k} = \pi, -\pi$ are equivalent. source: [2]	8
5	Schematic view of 3D TI : (a) Helical states of 3D Topological Insulator. No back scattering as the helical states are oppositely polarised. (b) Single 2D Dirac Cone on 2D Brillouin surface representing the energy dispersion. Energy as function of momentum component (x,y). Source: [2]	9
6	Representation of the atom-centered division of space in Voronoi cell construction. Each hexagonal area represents a site n centered at \mathbf{R}^n global vector. The global vector \mathbf{x} denote the any point on the cluster which is the vector sum of the global vector \mathbf{R} of center of single site and local vector \mathbf{r} which denotes a local point inside the site. To construct the Green functions in two points or sites other neighbour sites will be connected by connecting coefficient from structural Green function (reproduced from PhD thesis Bauer [4]).	17
7	Substitution of a Host atom (blue circle) by impurity (red circle): The impurity region (light and transparent green area) will be subject of impurity potential, therefore three type Green Function will be our concern. (i) Green Function in host area, (ii) Green function in impurity area, (iii) Green Function in impurity to host area.	19

8	fcc lattice: Consider 001-plane indicating magnetic moments of few atoms. Typical atomic shell around an atom shows that a red atom has 4 atoms (yellow atoms) at the first and second shell (red atoms) each. Thus the center atom isotropically interact with the same atoms in certain shell by equal strength. The interactions explains competitive interactions with opposite sign for different shells. Figure produced by VESTA [5].	23
9	Typical DMI interactions (a) , Left figure: Magnetic moment displacement on $\{010\}$ planes thus the resultant DMI vector along Y-axis. (b) , Right figure: Magnetic moment displacement on $[100]$ -plane, then the resultant DMI out of plane.	24
10	An Schematic overview of AiiDA Architecture showing different fundamental section. Source: [6].	27
11	A schematic provenance graph for multiply <i>CalcJob</i> calculation: With two input <i>Int</i> nodes the <i>CalcJob</i> returns one <i>Int</i> output node by accomplishing the successful multiply calculations. Distinctly, the rectangle symbols the process and the ellipse symbols the data nodes (green color). Each node is identified with the unique universal ID (inside the brackets). Source: [7]	29
12	<i>VoronoiCalculation</i> : The crystal structure, pre-compiled code and calculation parameters are the required inputs for <i>VoronoiCalculation</i> . The output <i>RemoteData</i> contain crystal shape function and starting potential required for the <i>KkrCalculation</i> . The output parameters <i>Dict</i> returns info of calculation e.g. code version, compiler info, cluster etc	32
13	Band structure workflow Combine three steps: (i) Validating the least mandatory inputs i.e <i>RemoteData</i> form the parent calculation, input parameters <i>Dict</i> and <i>KKR Code</i> (ii) running the band structure calculation step by returning the <i>FolderData</i> , and output parameters <i>Dict</i> . (iii) in final step the band structure data is parsed to the <i>ArrayData</i>	33
14	Flowchart for <i>combine_imp_wc</i> showing workflow plan.	34
15	Band structure plot for different SOC interactions.	34
16	Host crystal structure construct with <i>plot_kkr</i> from AiiDA-KKR tools [8]. Left: Unit cell used in simulation with primitive lattice vectors $\mathbf{a}=(2.19, 3.80, 0.0)\text{\AA}$, $\mathbf{b}=(-2.19, 3.80, 0.0)\text{\AA}$ and $\mathbf{c}=(0, -2.53, 10.16)\text{\AA}$. Empty sphere in between the atom layers that are needed for technical reason in the KKR method are omitted. Right: Visualisation of quintuple layers in (001) planes for modified structure for the sake of visibility. Te and Bi atoms are shown in golden and violet colors, respectively. The Te (Te1, Te2, Te3) and Bi (Bi1, Bi2) atoms are ascending numbered from top side to the bottom side of the left figure. The van der Waals gap is located in between Te2 and Te3.	36
17	DOS for bulk Bi_2Te_3 . DOS for all host atoms excluding the empty spheres.	37

18	(a) Spin integrated DOS of some 3d and 4d elements around Fermi level. (b) DOS at the Fermi level of d-block elements: Comparing with the benchmark elements Cr and V (limiting the DOS at Fermi level to 2.6 states per eV), the interested elements with the low density of states are Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, Y, Zr, Mo, Tc, Ru, Rh, Ag and Cd, where some are magnetic and some are not.	39
19	(a) Spin magnetic moments in unit of Bohr magneton (μ_B) for 3d and 4d transition metals embedded in host Bi_2Te_3 . The impurities with magnetic moments approximately $1\mu_B$, shown by red line, or larger are in our concern.(b) Hunds' rule for d-orbital electron filling. The larger number of unpaired electron response to the larger magnetic moment, for instance, Mn has largest magnetic moment.	41
20	Total magnetic momentum from two impurities. The impurities lie at two nearest neighbour cells and on the same Bi layer (Bi1 layer). Magnetic moments in column X come from single impurity calculation. The magnetic moments from the other columns reveal total magnetic moment calculated from double impurity calculations.	43
21	The figure shows the changes in magnetic moment, along x-axis, of first impurity atoms doped in the Bi layer (Bi1 atomic layer). The changes take place due to the insertion of the second impurity in next nearest neighbour cell and on the same Bi quintuple layer. The data in first column for symbol X represents the differences in magnetic moment without any insertion of the second impurity and therefore differences are be zero. The calculated Spin magnetic momentum are in the z-axis.	44
22	Heisenberg spin interaction, J_{ij} (in unit of meV) between magnetic moments of two impurity atoms i and j . The impurity pairs are corresponds to the impurity arrangement as Fig. 21. The red and blue colors represent ferromagnetic and anti-ferromagnetic interaction respectively.	45
23	Magnitude of anisotropic exchange interaction vector DMI, between the magnetic impurities arranged as same as arranged in Fig 20.	46
24	The ratio from magnitude of DMI vector to the J_{ji} interaction with the same impurity arrangement as the arrangement for 20. The cut-off J_{ij} value is 1 meV and below this value we do not take the ratio DMI to J in consideration.	47
25	Magnetic interaction J_{ij} for impurities in the same as well as different atomic layers. The plot group corresponds to the impurities in different layers has been represented by circular points (impurities in the same atomic layer represented by triangular points) and shifted by 10 meV for lucid visibility.	50

26	Magnetic interaction J_{ij} for impurities in the same as well as different atomic layers. The plots are represented as described in Fig 25.	51
27	Magnetic interaction J_{ij} which is obtained from the combination of the different plot groups (in Fig 25 and Fig 26) associated with impurities located in the same atomic layer and in different atomic layers.	52
28	Magnetic interaction J_{ij} which are analogous to the plots in Fig 27 by replacing impurity-1 by Mn and Mo.	53
29	DMI interaction, D_{ij} which contains interactions between impurities in the same atomic layer as well as in the different atomic layers. The impurity arrangements are the same as described in a sub-figure of Fig. 25.	55
30	DMI interaction, D_{ij} which contains interactions between impurities in the same atomic layer as well as in the different atomic layers. The impurity arrangements are the same as described in a sub-figure of Fig. 26.	56
31	Comparative pictures between the DMI and J_{ji} by their ratio and the impurities are arranged as described in Fig. 27. The competition are taken into account if the J_{ij} has minimum value 1meV otherwise set to zero.	58
32	Comparative pictures between the DMI and J_{ji} by their ratio as presented in Fig. 31 but with different impurity-1 (Mn and Mo).	59
33	Heisenberg Magnetic interactions J_{ij} between different atoms in different distances and in different atomic layers $Bi1$ and $Bi2$. Each sub-figure stands for J_{ij} (in meV) interaction with one specific element (from V, Cr, Mn, Mo) to the all of V, Cr, Mn, Mo. The asterisk data points stands for interactions between defects in the same Bi layer and the square graph points indicate interaction between the impurities in different Bi layers (the numbering of atomic layers has been discussed in Fig. 16).	61
34	Comparative pictures between the DMI and J_{ji} (in meV) from KKR-GF-CPA method. The plots describe the ratio in the same atomic layer (by asterisk points) as well as in the different atomic layers (by square points) with impurity arrangement as described in Fig. 33.	63
35	Analogous plot as described Fig. 31 with different impurities.	64
36	Linear Regression Model with 1600 training data set and 400 test data set: The model's R^2 score is 0.074 and error RMSE is 3.215 on test data group.	67
37	Kernel Ridge Regression on 1600 training data set and 400 test data set: The model's R^2 score is 0.614 and error RMSE is 2.076 on test data group.	68

38	Typical Algorithmic flowchart for Decision Tree model: Features $x^{(d)}$ are split by a threshold value m_d . The final subsets are called leaves and the splitting point between two branches or sub trees is called internal node.	69
39	Decision Tree regression and boosting it with AdaBoost: For test data group R^2 for DTR is 0.691, and RMSE is 1.859, and with boosting DTR the R^2 0.829 and RMSE 1.382. For training AdaBoost with DTR the $R^2=1.0$ and RMSE=0.00.	70
40	Relative Feature importance of DTR and it's boosting with AdaBoost.	71

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Topological Insulator (TI)	4
2.1	Quantum Hall effect(QHE):	4
2.2	Quantum spin Hall effect(QSHE)	6
2.3	Quantum anomalous Hall effect (QAHE)	6
2.4	The topological insulators	7
2.4.1	The Chern invariant	7
2.4.2	Z_2 topological insulator	8
2.4.3	2D topological insulator	9
2.4.4	3D topological insulator	9
3	KKR Green Function Approach	11
3.1	Density functional theory (DFT)	11
3.2	Green functions	12
3.3	Lippmann-Schwinger equation	13
3.4	Dyson equation	14
3.5	Green functions in solids	14
3.5.1	Free space Green function	15
3.5.2	Single-site Green function for a finite potential	15
3.5.3	KKR representation of the Green function	16
3.6	KKR impurity Green function	19
4	Atomistic Model of Magnetism	21
4.1	Extended Heisenberg model	22
4.2	Calculation of J_{ij} tensor elements	24
5	A Scalable Computational Infrastructure with AiiDA	26
5.1	AiiDA Architecture	27
5.1.1	Engine	28
5.1.2	Provenance graph model	28
5.1.3	Database abstraction and querying language	30
6	The AiiDA-KKR Plugin and Its Application	31
6.1	Calculations plugins	31
6.2	Workflow plugins	32
6.3	Tools	34
7	Magnetic Impurity Analysis in TI	35
7.1	Computational setup	35
7.2	Density of states in crystalline Bi_2Te_3	37
7.3	DOS for d-block transitional elements in Bi_2Te_3	38
7.4	Single impurity magnetic moment	40
7.5	Magnetic exchange coupling for double impurity calculations	42
7.5.1	Magnetic moments for a finite distance	43

7.5.2	Magnetic exchange interaction for a finite distance	45
7.5.3	Magnetic exchange interactions for different distances . .	49
7.6	Magnetic Interaction Analysis With CPA Calculation	60
8	Supervised Learning of J_{ij}	65
8.1	Regression of J_{ij}	66
8.1.1	Linear regression	66
8.1.2	Kernel Ridge regression	68
8.1.3	Decision trees regression	69
9	Conclusion and Outlook	72
9.1	Conclusion	72
9.2	Outlook	74

Abstract

Magnetic impurities and their long-range interaction (ferromagnetic) order play pivotal roles in the topological phase transition from QSHI to QAHI. This transition transforms helical edge states belonging to the QSHI for 2D TIs (surface states for 3D TI) to the chiral edge states in QAHI for 2D TIs (surface states for 3D TI). Due to such chiral states, the QAHI forbids back-scattering in electron conducting channels, which in turn provides dissipationless current and increases energy efficiency for conducting channels. The chiral states consist of single spin electrons which provide spin currents from conventional charge currents. Regarding the properties of QAHI, the QAHI opens a new venue for low-energy electronics, spintronics and quantum computation [9]. Independently, the V- [10] and Cr-doped [11] as well as their co-doping [12] $(\text{Sb, Bi})_2\text{Te}_3$ shows stable QAHE but with very low temperatures ($\leq 0.5\text{K}$). In this high throughput ab-initio work, we will investigate other possible co-doping, dimer calculations, from the d-block elements in 3D TI Bi_2Te_3 . For this purpose, we have extended AiiDA-KKR plugins by developing combine-impurity workflow called *combineimps_wc* using GF formulation of DFT code (KKR-GF method) and the new workflow is capable to run multi-impurity calculations. Here, the dimer calculations are in the main focus, and from the calculation results we will analyze Heisenberg isotropic collinear interaction (J_{ij}), Dzyaloshinskii–Moriya interaction (DMI, D_{ij}), and their ratio for each possible impurity couple. Finally, using the obtained J_{ij} data we have implemented some linear regression machine learning tools to understand better the dependency of J_{ij} on some well-known factors e.g. inter-impurity distance, electronegativity. Our results from the notion of this work will give a list of some potential impurities and after their potential impurity combinations for stable QAHE. It will also render an impression of implementation of machine learning approach for designing better magnetic interactions in TIs.

1 Introduction

In mathematics, topology allows to separate objects into classes that are equivalent under deformation, twisting, distorting, contracting and stretching without tearing or breaking of the original shape or space. Using smooth transformation different objects can be transformed into one another if they belong to the same that is characterized by a distinct distinct topological class *topological invariant*. In this sense of topology, a rectangle is equivalent to a circle, a sphere is equivalent to cylinder. On the other side, a torus is not equivalent to sphere [13] as a torus has a hole. In this example the topological invariant is the genus of the shapes that roughly speaking counts the number of holes in a geometrical shape. The concept of topological classification can also be applied to the electronic structure of solids.

An example where topology in solid state physics has important consequences is the quantum Hall effect (QHE). Materials, that show the QHE, show gapless edge states in an otherwise insulating phase if the materials is placed in a strong magnetic field. The number of conducting edge channels directly reflects the topological character and can be classified or counted by a topological invariant. The topological origin of this effect makes the edge states very robust and they can only vanish if a topological phase transition happens that typically goes in line with a closing and reopening of the energy gap in the bulk. However, owing to such special properties of these surface or edge states, it is highly interested for application ranging from the spintronics to quantum computation [14]. Other examples for topological properties are the Quantum Spin Hall Insulator (QSHI) and the Quantum Anomalous Hall Insulator (QAHI) which are the pivotal parts of this work. One of the most intriguing features of QSHI is their counter-propagating metallic surface states for spin up and spin down channel and they are protected by time-reversal symmetry (TRS). Distinctly, QAHI have only one propagating metallic surface states for one spin channel due to internal magnetic field that breaks time -reversal symmetry. One way to achieve this internal magnetic field is doping TI's with magnetic impurities.

The development of the theory behind Topological Insulator started in 1972 with the realization of the concept of the 2D Kosterlitz-Thouless phase transition which is caused by the interaction between the topological charges [15, 16]. Afterwards more theoretical and experimental efforts gave recognition of topologically characterized matter in condensed matter physics. For instance, the TKNN invariant [17] distinguishing a quantum hall state and an ordinary insulator, the integer quantum hall state [18, 19], the explanation of the quantum hall effect in band theory by a model of graphene in periodic magnetic field by Haldane in 1988 [20] are remarkable breakthrough. Recently, the contemporary efforts on the topological matter has been awarded with the Nobel Prize in physics in 2016 to D. J. Thouless, F. D. M. Haldane, and J. M. Kosterlitz for their work "Theoretical Discoveries of Topological Phase Transitions and Topological Phase of Matter"¹. Interestingly, both the theoretical and experimental development of different topological properties of matter is still an emerging

¹<https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/physics/2016/press-release/>

field of research. For instance, in recent years the new classes of Topological crystalline insulators [21, 22], topological superconductors [23, 24] or topological semimetals [25, 26, 27] were discovered.

The pivotal ingredient for topological insulator to expose the non-trivial topological states is the spin-orbit coupling (SOC). So, the traditional insulators and semiconductors containing heavy elements should be in the front line of candidates for topological materials [28]. For instance Bi/Sb alloy was the first 3D Topological insulator [29, 30] and commonly studied other strong topological insulators (TIs) are Bi_2Se_3 , Bi_2Te_3 and Sb_2Te_3 [28]. In this work, the material Bi_2Te_3 has been used as the bulk topological insulator for doping magnetic impurities, as the material has strong topological helical surface states [28]. When TIs are combined with an internal magnetic field the TRS get broken. This transforms the QSHI into the quantum anomalous hall insulator (QAHI). As a consequence instead of having of counter-propagating helical states the QAH state exhibits a single chiral edge state where the spin is locked to the momentum of the electrons. This work is the continuation of the Master thesis of Fabian Bertoldo² who conducted a high-throughput investigation on the transport properties of $(\text{Bi, Se})_2\text{Te}_3$. We will continue his investigation and focus on the magnetic interaction between multiple dopants. In particular we investigate transition metal impurities as well as the combination with Eu (Europium) as rare earth element. We seek to understand the magnetic interaction between the dopants and investigate the tendency for non-collinear magnetism with the help of the ratio between the magnitude of the Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya vector and the exchange interaction.

Nowadays, with increasing computing power as well as the development of the different advanced computational methods, it has become feasible to run the huge amounts of complex calculations. At the same time, tracking large amount of calculations running together, that might be in the order of few tens of thousands [6], as well as accessing their resultant data must be possible in a convenient way. Regarding this fact there some automated simulation tools and frameworks are available, for example, Fireworks [31] and AFLOW [32] in the domain of the material science. Also some others like Signac [33] and GC3Pie [34] are for general high-performance computing. For this thesis the most important tool is the AiiDA (Automated Interactive Infrastructure and Database for Computational Science) framework [6]. AiiDA provides not only almost all the facilities like other high-throughput and advanced simulation tools but ensures the reproducibility of the calculation results by storing the complete data provenance in a rational database. This implements the FAIR principles for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable data³.

The high-throughput calculations of this work are done with the AiiDA-KKR⁴ plugin [9]. Fundamentally, AiiDA-KKR plugin builds upon the full potential full-relativistic real-space all-electron density functional code in JuKKR⁵ (Jülich

²https://www.fz-juelich.de/pgi/pgi-1/EN/Leistungen/MasterDiplomDr/_node.html

³<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴<https://github.com/JuDFTteam/aiida-kr>

⁵<https://iffgit.fz-juelich.de>

Korringa-Kohn-Rostoker) code package [4]. DFT codes with the JuKKR package are based on the Korringa-Kohn-Rostoker Green function method which allows to calculate electronic structure, magnetic properties with spin-orbit coupling and non-collinear magnetism or transport properties. Here we extend the AiiDA-KKR plugin and develop a combine-impurity workflow called as *combineimps_wc*. This new workflow combines and runs two pre-converged single impurity clusters or one single impurity cluster and one multi-impurity cluster into a larger impurity system. This is then used to calculate the magnetic exchange interactions among magnetic impurities in the Bi_2Te_3 topological insulator.

Machine learning approaches can be employed to learn a data ensemble and to scale data dependencies on the fundamental properties of the data. Probably, one important use of machine learning in condensed matter physics to find new potential materials in no-frills experiments while the material might be predicted from the theoretical side or some other correlations between the different existing materials. Machine learning approaches outweigh the experimental efforts by reducing the time needed for conducting an experiment for a long period in extremely certain materials. On the other way, the approach alleviates the financial budgets required for equipment and resources. Indeed, a combination of the development of the computation methods, computer simulation, machine learning, and the experiments substantially allows cutting time and cost [35]. Here, the data group of the magnetic interaction parameters of Heisenberg extended model obtained from this high-throughput calculations has been subjected to some supervised machine learning models.

The work has been organised as follows: in chapter-2 we have discussed a general overview of QHE, QSHE, QAHE and other topological types relevant to this work. The GF formulation of DFT theory has been illustrated in chapter-3, KKR-Green Function Approach. The chapter-4 includes Heisenberg extended model describing the isotropic exchange interaction and DMI. The next chapters-5 and -6 aim to represent the concept automation simulation software in computational science and the development of AiiDA-KKR respective. In the chapter-7 we will represent the magnetic data from this high-throughput calculation work. Later, supervised learning approach has been used in chapter-8 on the J_{ij} interaction data. Next what we have done in this work and what we have found in this work are summarised in chapter-9. Finally, how the work can be continued further in different aspect and what will be the outcomes of this work has been discussed in chapter-9.2.

2 Topological Insulator (TI)

To describe the Topology in the condensed matter physics phase transition plays an important key [15]. The phase or the electronic structure can be distinguished by the topological numbers which leads to the topological classes. The theoretical analysis of such electronic structures predicts measurable physical quantities. The quantities are extremely robust owing to the fact that the topological numbers are invariant. In other words, to destroy the properties that follow from the topology of a crystal, some specific properties of electronic structure of crystal need to be changed or destroyed. All the topological classes can not be describe under any universal theory, saying the first principle electronic band theory framework [36]. However, to understand the fundamental properties of TIs band theory plays key role and it is really inspiring that even after 90 years still the band theory is revealing its intrinsic treasures.

In this section we attempt to explain the historical example quantum Hall effect (QHE) TIs, afterwards near cousin quantum the spin Hall (QSHI) insulator and finally to the quantum anomalous Hall insulator (QAHI).

2.1 Quantum Hall effect(QHE):

By Bloch theorem, electronic states can be labeled by the crystal momentum \vec{k} defined in the Brillouin zone. By exploiting the translational symmetry, crystal momentum can be considered as a good quantum number. For any Bloch states $|u_m(\vec{k})\rangle$ the eigenvalues for Bloch Hamiltonian $H(\vec{k})$ define energy band for the m -th band. As \vec{k} is a quantum number it can not change continuously from one band to another. So, all topologically trivial semiconductors and insulators, though they have different size of energy gap, are topologically equivalent as band gap can not vanish [14]. All the insulators with the energy gap are equivalent vacuum [14].

However not all materials with a band gap in their electronic structure are topologically equivalent to the vacuum. Instead, an exotic state of quantum matter called Integer Quantum Hall state had been explained by von Klitzing, Dorda and Pepper in 1980 [18, 19]. For elucidation purpose in figure-1, consider 2D electron system subject to the magnetic field along z-axis and electric field perpendicular to the plane. The loosely bound electrons will exhibit quantized cyclotron motion of frequency ω_c . This kind of cyclotron motion in the edges leads to Landau levels of energy $\epsilon_m = \hbar\omega_c(m + 1/2)$ and the cyclotron orbits in the bulk region exhibits insulating states. At the edges of the crystal the cyclotron orbits cannot close. This leads to the skipping orbits that propagate along the edges. Their quantized Hall conductivity is given as

$$\sigma_{xy} = N(e^2/h) \tag{1}$$

with the quantized factor e^2/h and N is integer quantum number ⁶.

⁶N is also called filling factor of landau level. Every landau level is degenerated. N is

Figure 1: Quantum Hall Effect. The skipping orbits on the edges moves different direction for electron (towards left) and holes (towards right). The electrons on the bulk region are in the circular motion rather than drift motion responsible for bulk insulating phase. source: [1]

Another attempt to explain the QHE under the band structure theory leads to the TKNN topological invariant by Thouless, Kohmoto, Nightingale and den Nijs in 1982 [17]. By gluing the ends of the 2D crystal Magnetic Brillouin zone, it is easy to represent them as torus (by respecting periodicity at each degree of freedom x and y). Crystal momentum \vec{k} on torus can be mapped to the Bloch Hamiltonian $H(\vec{k})$. The band structures, which are topologically equivalent, can be transformed into one another without affecting their topological properties. Such topologically equivalent structures classify the materials into different topological classes distinguished by topological invariant n ($n \in \mathbb{Z}$, integers) called Chern or TKNN invariant. According to TKNN, the Chern number or global Chern number n is identical to N in Eq(1) [17]. The global Chern number is defined as a summation of all local Chern numbers in different occupied bands.

The band structure of the non-trivial topological insulator renders the excited band energy gap only in the bulk region. On the surface gapless boundary states appear. These boundary states are protected by the bulk excitation gap and can be removed by closing the bulk gap. The relation between the bulk-boundary states is called *bulk-boundary correspondence*. The changes of the energy gap from the bulk region ($n = 0$ no conducting states) to the boundary ($n = 1$, 'one-way' conducting states) occurs if some points in-between bulk and boundary the energy gap vanishes [14]. Such interconnection between the topology and gapless modes was founded by Jackiw and Rebbi (1976) [37] and later by Su, Schrieffer and Heeger [38].

defined as electron density (both spin up and down) divided by density of degenerate states of Landau level. This discussion is beyond of our topic.

2.2 Quantum spin Hall effect(QSHE)

The QSHE can be thought as quantum Hall effect for two different spin channel satisfying the TRS as TRS flips both spin and conductivity σ_{xy} . So the hall conductivity are in opposite direction for two spin up and spin down channels. Each of them have the same magnitude (for the same spin density) ($\sigma_{xy\downarrow} = e^2/h$, $\sigma_{xy\uparrow} = -e^2/h$). In this sense, though the total Hall conductivity is zero but it renders quantized spin Hall conductivity. The states associated with the different spin channels are termed '**helical**' [39], in analogy with spin-momentum helicity of a particle. These 1D helical edge states currents in the opposite directions (Fig. 2(a)).

Figure 2: 2D QSHE with Dirac dispersion: (a) Two 1D edge states for spin up and down in opposite directions. (b) Dispersion of two non degenerate spin states. The crossing point or Dirac point, is the meeting point for conduction and valence band. source: [2]

This kind of system builds up due to strong spin-orbit couplings and smooth transformation of the Hamiltonian from bulk region towards the surface [28]. At the bulk region the transition of the Hamiltonian closes the band gap and reopens it again. The new band structure swaps the states from different orbital bands⁷. This process of band closing and opening is called band inversion and the transformed band structure can be distinguished as inverted band structure. The inversion takes place by smooth transformation of Hamiltonian from the bulk region towards the vacuum through the surface. The inverted band structure gets re-inverted in the vacuum as trivial insulator. Such transformation of the band structure yields the stable Dirac-point at the surface of the material (Fig. 2(b)) which gives robust surface states of two spin channel.

2.3 Quantum anomalous Hall effect (QAHE)

The QAHE can be elucidated as the combination of the QHE and QSHE, and is found when TRS of QSHI is broken due to the magnetization from the magnetic doping into the QSHE system. As TRS is broken between the counter propagating helical states in 2D TIs by induced magnetic effect. The resulting edge

⁷One good explanatory figure will shown in AiiDA-KKR Plugins part which shows the band inversion in the bulk region. The figure has been created with the help kkr_bs_wc workflow developed in this work

conducting states consist of one spin channel in one direction. This conversion of quantum spin Hall effect is known as quantum anomalous hall effect (QAHE on 1881) [40]. In 3D topological insulator, the strong ferromagnetic moment (FM) order opens the gap of Dirac cone or 2D Dirac fermions on the surfaces (bottom and top) perpendicular to magnetization. Which results the gapless metallic states for one spin channel that carries Hall current along the edges or magnetic domain wall.

A general sketch about the three types of distinct topological effects are laid bare in figure-3. In general, Topological insulators (TIs), an exotic state of

Figure 3: Schematic of the three topological effects with the year of experimental discoveries in the brackets. The edge states for different spin channels are indicated with different colors. The labels \vec{B} and \vec{M} represent the external magnetic field and internal magnetization due to magnetic doping, respectively [3]

quantum system, have well defined insulating properties in the bulk region but possess metallic surface states or edge states which yields the conductivity at the boundary of the material

2.4 The topological insulators

2.4.1 The Chern invariant

The Chern number of topological invariant is analogous to the QHE as discussed in the quantum Hall effect section. One can contrast between the ordinary insulator and the insulating properties in QHE by Eq. 1. In the absence of the external magnetic field as well as Landau level and under broken time reversal symmetry, the band structure associated with this topological insulator is classified by the topological invariant Chern number $n \in Z$ or TKNN invariant (Thouless, Kohmoto, Nightingale, and den Nijs) [41]. The band structures can be transformed from to other band structure of the same topological class. The transformation must take in smooth manner without closing the existent band gap in the process of transformation. The total Chern number is the summation of the local Chern number for all occupied bands, $n = \sum_m n_m$ for m bands. According to the TKNN, this number is equivalent to the N in Eq. 1. One fundamental consequence of the topological classification is the quantized conducting chiral edge states with $n > 0$ which requires breaking of time reversal symmetry and trivial insulating states $n = 0$.

2.4.2 Z_2 topological insulator

As discussed earlier, Chern insulators evolve from the quantum Hall effect (QHE) and occurs when time-reversal-symmetry (TRS) is broken under effective magnetic field. However, another distinct Topological class associated with the spin-orbit interaction under preservation of the TRS had been found by Kane and Male [42]. The topological class from this spin-orbit interaction can be understood examining the role of time reversal symmetry on the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle.

Figure 4: Two Kramers pairs at the edges from spin-orbit couplings. Each Kramers pairs belongs two Time-Reversal-Invariant-Momentum (TRIM, points of degeneracy of band structure) points at $\vec{k} = \pi, 0$. The points come at the $\vec{k} = -\pi, 0$ due to the periodicity of the Brillouin zone. Therefore TRIMs corresponds to a Kramer pairs at $\vec{k} = \pi, -\pi$ are equivalent. source: [2]

A TRS operator for a spin-half particle can be represented by anti-unitary operator Θ ,

$$\Theta = \exp\{(i\pi S_y/\hbar)\}K \quad (2)$$

where S_y Pauli y-spin component, K complex conjugate operator. Under the TRS invariant Bloch Hamiltonian satisfies the following relation,

$$\Theta H(\vec{k})\Theta^{-1} = H(-\vec{k}) \quad (3)$$

Eq. 3 provides that energy bands under TRS invariant come in pairs for momentum $+\vec{k}$ and $-\vec{k}$ in Fig. 4. Thus, the smooth deformation of the Hamiltonian without closing the band gap gives the TKNN invariant $n=0$. Kane and Male [43] argue that there is another Chern number $N_k = 0$ or 1.

With time reversal and space inversion, the states associated with $+\vec{k}$ and $-\vec{k}$ are designated as Kramer pairs. In Fig. 4, there are two Kramer pairs are represented. According to Kramer's theorem the pairs are two fold degenerated at $\vec{k} = 0, \pi$ (considering half of the Brillouin zone, as one half is the mirror of

other). These points corresponding to the degeneracy ($\Lambda_{1,2}$) in the space, here $\vec{k} = 0$ and $\vec{k} = +\pi$, are called Time-Reversal-Invariant-Momentum (TRIM). The existence of $\Lambda_{1,2}$ points at $\vec{k} = 0, \pi$ can lead to the stable edge states. Let us consider the right part (half Brillouin zone 0 to π) of the Kramer's pair in Fig. 4. Two TRIM points are connected by electronic states. If the connecting states between the two TRIM points intersect the Fermi energy level by even number then the edge states can be removed from the Fermi level by a smooth transformation that shifts the bands up and down [14]. Otherwise for the odd number of total intersection of Fermi level by Kramer's pair give stable conducting edge states. This conducting states is represented by Chern number $N_k = 1$. This describes the stability of Dirac point at the edge. The mechanism can be generalised also for 3D TIs. There are several mathematical mechanism are available to calculate the integer values Z_2 invariant [43, 29, 44, 45, 46, 47] associated with this TRIMs.

2.4.3 2D topological insulator

Quantum Spin Hall Insulator is an example of 2D Topological insulator. The conducting edge states of a 2D Topological Insulator are associated with the single 1D Dirac-cone. This 1D Dirac cone gives the edges states of the opposite spins moving parallel and anti-parallel [28]. Reducing the dimensionality of quantum well or in slabs of 3D topological insulators can lead 2D class. It is anticipated that the thin films form the 3D TIs, for instance Bi/Sb, Bi_2Te_3 , Bi_2Se_3 , and $\text{Ge}(\text{Bi}, \text{Sb})_2\text{Te}_4$, are belong to the 2D TIs [48, 49, 50, 51, 52].

2.4.4 3D topological insulator

Figure 5: Schematic view of 3D TI : (a) Helical states of 3D Topological Insulator. No back scattering as the helical states are oppositely polarised. (b) Single 2D Dirac Cone on 2D Brillouin surface representing the energy dispersion. Energy as function of momentum component (x,y). Source: [2]

In 2006, three theoretical groups had realised the 3D nature of the quantum spin Hall insulator [53, 44, 54]. A 3D TI is characterised by four Z_2 topological invariants $(\nu_0; \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3)$ [53, 44, 54]. 3D TIs belong protected surface states as shown in figure 6(a). The surface states can be considered as states in 2D crystal momentum. Each surface has four TRIM points $\Lambda_{1,2,3,4}$ in the Brillouin Zone (figure-5). If the joining lines between the two points Γ_a and Γ_b intersect the Fermi surface by an odd number, then a 2D Dirac cone on that surface will provide protected surface states. These surface states provide counter-propagating spin-momentum locking or helical states. As the surface states behave like 2D TIs, by stacking the 2D QSHI layers it is possible to construct a 3D Topological insulator [14].

3 KKR Green Function Approach

Quantum mechanical simulation based on density functional theory (DFT) is an important tool in computational materials science. The approach of many particles problem, that the Schrödinger equation poses, needs huge amount of memory and computational cost [4]. Instead of computing directly the many particle wave function solutions to the Schrödinger's equation, DFT uses electronic density to determine the ground state properties of system. The DFT theory assumes the physical system as an effective single particle system described by the functional of the electron density [55, 56]. Today's practical importance of DFT theory has been discussed by R. O. Jones. He showed that the number of the DFT based research papers has stepped up from 5000 publications per year in 2000 to more than 15000 per year in 2015 [57].

The Korringa-Kohn-Rostoker Green function approach (KKR-GF) is a specific implementation of DFT. It is especially well suited to deal with disorder and magnetic systems [58]. In contrast to wave function based methods, the KKR-GF approach calculates the Green function that is the resolvent of the Hamiltonian. Beyond solving the impurity problem, the KKR-GF method has a wide range of applications including for instance the calculation of transport properties in dilute metallic alloys [59]. In this chapter we will describe DFT and KKR method mainly from the PhD thesis of Bauer [4] and an article by Mavropoulos [59]⁸.

3.1 Density functional theory (DFT)

In the 1960s Hohenberg and Kohn argued that the information of the ground state wave function can be obtained from the ground state electron density of a given system [60]. According to the Hohenberg and Kohn the many particle wave function for the ground state is a unique functional density n

$$\psi_0(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, \dots, \vec{r}_m) = \psi_0[n] \quad (4)$$

Where the system m particles locate at $\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, \dots, \vec{r}_m$. The energies and other observables are expressed from the density functional. The total energy is also a functional of density

$$\begin{aligned} E[n] &= \langle \psi[n] | \mathcal{H} | \psi[n] \rangle \\ &= T[n] + U[n] + V[n] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{H} is the Hamiltonian operator for total energy of system, T is the kinetic energy, U is the potential energy from the electron-electron interaction and V is potential electron-nuclei interaction and all terms are dependent only on the electron density.

⁸In this chapter we will not give any deeper or illustrative derivation rather we will focus on the conceptual development of the KKR Green function by basic equations of physics discussed here.

Later, Kohn and Sham [61] added an effective medium of fictitious non-interacting electron interaction replacing of full many-body interaction. The condition is that the ground state density of the new system should be equivalent to the real ground state of many-body wave function. In this approximation, an additional exchange energy functional E_{xc} is introduced with the Eq. 5 which becomes

$$E[n] = T_s[n] + U_H[n] + V[n] + E_{xc}[n] \quad (6)$$

Where T_s is the kinetic energy from the single particle kinetic energy, U_H is the Hartree energy giving the classical electrostatic energy of electrons, V is the energy due to the nuclei and external field. Finally the exchange interaction energy E_{xc} is evolved from the energy differences $(U - U_H)$, $(T - T_s)$ and other quantum mechanical interaction. The Kohn-Sham equation Eq. 6 is equivalent to the single particle Schrödinger equation as

$$\left(-\nabla^2 + \int_V d\vec{r}' \frac{n(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r}' - \vec{r}|} + V_{ext}(\vec{r}) + \frac{\delta E_{xc}[n]}{\delta n(\vec{r})} \right) \phi_i(\vec{r}) = \epsilon_i \phi_i(\vec{r}) \quad (7)$$

where $\phi_i(\vec{r})$ is called Kohn-Sham orbital and solution to the Eq. 6 with eigenvalue ϵ_i . The term E_{xc} formally contains all deviations from the single particle picture which can not be solved exact but for which approximations have to be applied. The more accurate measurement or approximation of E_{xc} defines the finer result of the DFT theory. To calculate the term E_{xc} , one good and important approximation is the Local Spin Density Approximation (LSDA). The LSDA has been used for simulation in this work.

3.2 Green functions

The Green function for linear differential operator $(z - \mathbf{L})$ is given as

$$(z - \mathbf{L})G(x, x') = \delta(x, x') \quad (8)$$

where z is the complex number. The Green function can be expressed as $G = \frac{\delta(x, x')}{(z - \mathbf{L})}$. The solution of inhomogeneous equation

$$(z - \mathbf{L})f = k \quad (9)$$

can be written as

$$f(x) = f_0(x) + \int dx' G(x, x'; z)k(x') \quad (10)$$

The solution, Eq. 10, has two parts. The first part $f_0(x)$ comes from the homogeneous solution of Eq. 9 and the second part is the inhomogeneous solution using the Green function from Eq. 8.

In the physics, the Green function equation corresponding to Eq. 8 can be defined as

$$(\epsilon - \mathcal{H})\mathcal{G}(\epsilon) = \hat{1} \quad (11)$$

with the complex energy $\epsilon = E + i\delta$ consists of real E and δ . Where \mathcal{H} defines the Hamiltonian of time-independent Schrödinger equation. The Green function is expressed as

$$\mathcal{G}(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\epsilon - \mathcal{H}} \quad (12)$$

In the Eq.12 the green function can be calculated for a system of known Hamiltonian. For known eigen-states of Hamiltonian \mathcal{H} the Green function gives the following spectral representation

$$\mathcal{G}(\epsilon) = \sum_i \frac{|\psi\rangle_i \langle\psi|_i}{\epsilon - \epsilon_i} \quad (13)$$

where the ϵ is the eigenvalue of eigen-states $|\psi\rangle$. The Eq. 13 give spectral for electron bound states $|\psi\rangle$. The Green function itself contains all the necessary physical information of the state as like as wave function. So any observable can be obtained from the Green function as

$$\langle\mathcal{A}\rangle = -\frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} \int_{-\infty}^{\epsilon_F} d\epsilon \text{Tr} \left(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{G}(\epsilon) \right) \quad (14)$$

where the integral is to be evaluated up-to the Fermi energy level for $T = 0$. In general, one can extend the integral to infinity and add a Fermi factor $f(\epsilon)$ to describe the occupation of the states depending on the temperature.

3.3 Lippmann-Schwinger equation

The unperturbed (e.g. in the free space) and perturbed wave equations for an energy eigen value ϵ are represented as

$$(\epsilon - \mathcal{H}_o) |\psi_o\rangle = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$(\epsilon - \mathcal{H}_o) |\psi\rangle = \Delta\mathcal{V} |\psi\rangle \quad (16)$$

where \mathcal{H}_o is the Hamiltonian of potential free system i.e. Kinetic energy, $|\psi\rangle$ is the wave function in field of potential $\Delta\mathcal{V}$. The equations correspond to the homogeneous and inhomogeneous part of the Schrodinger equation. Using the approach as for solution Eq. 10 and the resolvent Eq. 12, the solution for Eq. 16 is written as

$$|\psi\rangle = |\psi_o\rangle + \mathcal{G}_o \Delta\mathcal{V} |\psi\rangle \quad (17)$$

the Green function \mathcal{G}_o is the Green function associated with \mathcal{H}_o and defined as $\mathcal{G}_o = \frac{1}{\epsilon - \mathcal{H}_o}$. After recursive occurrences of the multiple scattering

$$|\psi\rangle = |\psi_o\rangle + \mathcal{G}_o (\Delta\mathcal{V} + \Delta\mathcal{V}\mathcal{G}_o\Delta\mathcal{V} + \dots) |\psi_o\rangle \quad (18)$$

The Eqs. 17 and 18 are called Lippmann-Schwinger equation. The equation gives wave function $|\psi\rangle$ after occurring of multiple action or scattering of the incoming wave function $|\psi_o\rangle$.

3.4 Dyson equation

Let us consider a new and unknown Green function, \mathcal{G} , due to perturbation change in Hamiltonian \mathcal{H}_0 in Eq.12.

$$\mathcal{G}(\epsilon) = (\epsilon - (\mathcal{H}_0 + \Delta\mathcal{V}))^{-1} \quad (19)$$

$$(\epsilon - (\mathcal{H}_0 + \Delta\mathcal{V}))\mathcal{G} = 1 \quad (20)$$

$$(\epsilon - \mathcal{H}_0)\mathcal{G} = 1 + \Delta\mathcal{V}\mathcal{G} \quad (21)$$

$$\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}_o + \mathcal{G}_o\Delta\mathcal{V}\mathcal{G} \quad (22)$$

where $\mathcal{G}_o = \frac{1}{\epsilon - \mathcal{H}_0}$. The subsequent insertion of \mathcal{G} gives

$$\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}_o + \mathcal{G}_o(\Delta\mathcal{V} + \Delta\mathcal{V}\mathcal{G}_o\Delta\mathcal{V} + \dots)\mathcal{G}_o \quad (23)$$

Both Eq. 22 and Eq. 23 are equivalent and called Dyson equation. Eq.23 represents construction of a new Green function (\mathcal{G}) due to the multiple actions ($\Delta\mathcal{V}$) on the known Green function (\mathcal{G}_o). This Highlights the multi-scattering events. In the multi-scattering interpretation, \mathcal{G}_o represents free space Green function and \mathcal{G} is Green function after n (the number of terms in the parentheses) scattering events. In between the scattering events the electron travel through free space and comes back to the potential space where scattering take place. The free space travel is indicated by \mathcal{G}_o , thus \mathcal{G}_o is free space electron propagator. Eq. 23 serves a pivotal role in the KKR Green function theory. By introducing the \mathcal{T} -matrix (\mathcal{T} -matrix also comes in Lippmann-Schwinger Eq. 18) the Dyson equation

$$\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}_o + \mathcal{G}_o\mathcal{T}\mathcal{G}_o \quad (24)$$

Thereafter, the \mathcal{T} -matrix can be written in the same type of expression as Dyson equation and Lippmann-Schwinger equation as

$$\mathcal{T} = \Delta\mathcal{V} + \Delta\mathcal{V}\mathcal{G}_o\mathcal{T} \quad (25)$$

3.5 Green functions in solids

Crystalline solids are build up by atoms in a periodic lattice. Therefore it is beneficial to represent the Green function in an atom centered basis. For numerical computation purpose, Green function of crystal is divided into the single site local Green function problems independently. The calculated individual local Green functions (describing a site of cluster) are connected themselves with the connecting coefficients. The connecting coefficients are obtained from the structural Green function. Here we mostly use the Dyson equation and Lippmann-Schwinger equation to get global Green function (describing any two points in cluster) of lattice from free space global green function.

3.5.1 Free space Green function

The potential-free green function or free space green function is expressed as

$$g(\vec{x}, \vec{x}'; \epsilon) = -\frac{\exp\left(ik|\vec{x} - \vec{x}'|\right)}{4\pi|\vec{x} - \vec{x}'|}, \quad k = \sqrt{\epsilon} \quad (26)$$

Expanding the Green function into real space harmonics Y_L

$$g(\vec{x}, \vec{x}'; \epsilon) = \sum_L (Y_L(\vec{x}; \epsilon) g_l(x, x'; \epsilon) Y_L(\vec{x}'; \epsilon)) \quad (27)$$

The radial Green function $g_l(x, x')$ is the combination of the Bessel (j_l) and Hankel function (h_l) which are the solutions of the potential free Schrödinger equation in spherical representation.

$$g_l(\vec{x}, \vec{x}'; \epsilon) = \sqrt{\epsilon} j_l(\sqrt{\epsilon}; x_<) h_l(\sqrt{\epsilon}; x_>) \quad (28)$$

The Green function for potential free space stands as

$$g(x, x'; \epsilon) = \sum_L \sqrt{\epsilon} j_L(x_<; \epsilon) h_L(x_>; \epsilon) \quad (29)$$

where $h_L(x_>; \epsilon) = j_L(\vec{x}) h_l(x_>; \epsilon)$ and $j_L(x_>; \epsilon) = Y_L(\vec{x}) j_l(x_>; \epsilon)$ are irregular and regular solutions respectively. The notation $r_<$ and $r_>$ indicate smaller and larger of the radii r and r' respectively.

3.5.2 Single-site Green function for a finite potential

For an explanation of the single-site Green Function (local GF) and their connections with other local GF via a global variable, let us consider a representation of the atom-centered division of space in Voronoi cells in Fig. 6. The Voronoi construction gives a polyhedron-shaped cell for each atom centered on the nucleus. The potential of each atom is considered as muffin-tin (MT) approximation (in MT the potential exist in a sphere confined in a polyhedron otherwise zero). The MT can be divided into a three dimensional logarithmic mesh grid. This logarithmic grid accounts for the rapid decrease of the potential with $\frac{1}{r}$. By taking of mesh grid, the local GF associated with a single polyhedron cell (say n^{th} cell) is calculated with respect to the local variable \vec{r} . Thus local GF explains the physical properties of the local n^{th} cell centered at vector \vec{R}^n , which is independent of other sites in the cluster. The local GF will be connected with other neighbour local GFs providing the global GF described with global variable \vec{x} where $\vec{x} = \vec{R}^n + \vec{r}$. Mathematically, the global variable

$$G(\vec{x}, \vec{x}') = G(\vec{R}^n + \vec{r}, \vec{R}^{n'} + \vec{r}') \quad (30)$$

The connections among the local GF is construct by the structural Green function, which mainly provides the connecting coefficients among the different local GF. In other words the connecting coefficients describe the strength of shadow effects of neighbour GF to the subject GF.

Here we will discuss construction of the local GF and depending on the description above we will discuss the multiple scattering as well as KKR representation of the GF in the next section.

Let us consider Schrödinger equation for a potential $V^n(\vec{r})$ in region of radius $\vec{R}^n(\vec{r}) = \vec{R}^n + \vec{r}$. The regular $R_l(\vec{r})$ and irregular $S_l(\vec{r})$ solutions⁹ for the single-potential scattering problem can be expressed using the Lippmann-Schwinger equation (Eq.17)

$$R_l^n(\vec{r}) = j_l(\vec{r}) + \int_0^{R_r} dr' g(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') V^n(\vec{r}') R_l^n(\vec{r}') \quad (31)$$

introducing the Eq.29 for a specific angular momentum l

$$R_l^n(\vec{r}) = j_l(\vec{r}) + \sqrt{\epsilon} h_l(r_>; \epsilon) \int_0^{R_r} dr' j_l(r_<; \epsilon) V^n(\vec{r}') R_l^n(\vec{r}') \quad (32)$$

$$R_l^n(\vec{r}) = j_l(\vec{r}) + \sqrt{\epsilon} t_l^n(\epsilon) h_l(r_>; \epsilon) \quad (33)$$

and

$$S_l(\vec{r}; \epsilon) = h_l(r_>; \epsilon) \quad (34)$$

where h_l and j_l are irregular and regular single site solution in free space. The $t_l^n = \int_0^{R_r} dr' j_l^n(r_<; \epsilon) V^n(\vec{r}') R_l^n(\vec{r}')$ is called single site t-matrix giving the strength of scattering from potential $V^n(\vec{r})$.

Equation 33 explains the sum of the potential free regular wave function j_l and the change in wave function due to single site scattering. The resultant regular wave function gives the scattered regular wave part going out of the potential region. The expression for single site Green function for a finite potential is

$$G_s(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \epsilon) = \sqrt{\epsilon} \sum_L R_L(r_<; \epsilon) Y_L(\vec{r}) S_L(r'_>; \epsilon) Y_L(\vec{r}') \quad (35)$$

$$G_s(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \epsilon) = \sqrt{\epsilon} \sum_L R_L(r_<; \epsilon) S_L(r'_>; \epsilon) \quad (36)$$

In this Eq. 36 obtained from scattering problem, the regular function $R_L(\vec{r})$ behaves like Bessel function and the irregular function $S_L(\vec{r}')$ behave like the Hankel function as in the potential free Green function Eq. 28.

3.5.3 KKR representation of the Green function

In solid, a lattice of atoms needs to be considered which introduces multiple scattering from one atom to the next. Using the multiple scattering problem, one can construct structural Green function for the considered lattice. Fig. 6 gives a general overview of multi-scattering problem.

⁹The subscript l indicates solutions are independent of the real spherical harmonics, while L stands for inclusion of real spherical harmonics with corresponding term.

Figure 6: Representation of the atom-centered division of space in Voronoi cell construction. Each hexagonal area represents a site n centered at \mathbf{R}^n global vector. The global vector \mathbf{x} denote the any point on the cluster which is the vector sum of the global vector \mathbf{R} of center of single site and local vector \mathbf{r} which denotes a local point inside the site. To construct the Green functions in two points or sites other neighbour sites will be connected by connecting coefficient from structural Green function (reproduced from PhD thesis Bauer [4]).

The Green function for two sites n and n' in free space is written as

$$g^{nn'}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \epsilon) = \delta_{nn'} g_s^{nn'}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \epsilon) + \sum_{L, L'} j_L(\vec{r}; \epsilon) g_{LL'}^{nn'}(\epsilon) j_{L'}(\vec{r}'; \epsilon) \quad (37)$$

Using the free space Green function Eq. 29

$$g^{nn'}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \epsilon) = \delta_{nn'} \sqrt{\epsilon} \sum_L j_L(x_{<}; \epsilon) h_L(x_{>}; \epsilon) + \sum_{L, L'} j_L(\vec{r}; \epsilon) g_{LL'}^{nn'}(\epsilon) j_{L'}(\vec{r}'; \epsilon) \quad (38)$$

In Eq. 38, the first term is the single site free space Green function and the second term is the multi-scattering contribution. The symbol $g_{LL'}^{nn'}$ is called potential free structural green function. The expansion coefficients are given by,

$$g_{LL'}^{nn'}(\epsilon) = 4\pi(1 - \delta_{nn'}) \sum_{L''} (i^{l-l'+l''} C_{LL'L''} h_{L''}(\vec{R}^n - \vec{R}^{n'}; \epsilon)) \quad (39)$$

where $C_{LL'L''}$ is called Gaunt coefficients and it is vanished when $l'' > l' + l$. The Gaunt coefficients is given as

$$C_{LL'L''} = \int d\Omega Y_L(\vec{r}) Y_{L'}(\vec{r}) Y_{L''}(\vec{r}) \quad (40)$$

In Eq. 39 it is also visible that the structural Green function ($g_{LL'}^{nn'}(\epsilon)$) is involved with irregular wave function of connecting center of the sites rather than the local points belonged to sites. Using the Dyson equation the potential free structural Green function can be turned into the structural Green function which includes site potentials.

$$G_{LL'}^{nn'}(\epsilon) = g_{LL'}^{nn'} + \sum_{n''} \sum_{L''L'''} g_{LL''}^{nn''} t_{L''L'''}^{n''} G_{L''L'}^{n''n'} \quad (41)$$

The Eq. 41 is called structural Dyson equation. The first term is the potential free structural Green function and the second term is the contribution from the multiple scattering to the structural Green function. The second term indicates that the Green function from a site n associated with a orbital L to the site n' associated with a orbital L' includes all the possible Green functions from intermediate multiple scattering. An element $t_{L''L'''}^{n''}$ of the t-matrix $t_{L''L'''}^{n''}$ can be described as an incoming spherical wave associated with orbital momentum L'' transformed into the spherical wave associated with orbital momentum L''' after scattering from the potential $\Delta V^{n''}$ of n'' th site. The second term also indicates infinite series of scattering process as

$$G_{LL'}^{nn'}(\epsilon) = g_{LL';m}^{nn'} + \sum_{n''} \sum_{L''L'''} g_{LL''}^{nn''} t_{L''L'''}^{n''} (g_{L''L'}^{n''n'}; m + \sum_{n'''} \sum_{L'''L''''} g_{L'''L''''}^{n''n'''} t_{L''''L'''''}^{n'''} (g_{L''''L'}^{n''n'''} + \dots)) \quad (42)$$

The Eq.41 or Eq. 42 gives the similar interpretation as Eq.18 and Eq.23. The red lines in Fig. 6 represent the structural Green function from site n to the site n' and some other parts due to the multiple scattering which equivalent to Eq.42.

Therefore, Green function for a finite potential $V(\vec{r})$ between sites n and n' is given

$$G^{nn'}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \epsilon) = \delta_{nn'} G_s^{nn'}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \epsilon) + \sum_{L, L'} R_L^n(\vec{r}; \epsilon) G_{LL'}^{nn'}(\epsilon) R_{L'}^{n'}(\vec{r}'; \epsilon) \quad (43)$$

Here, the first term gives single site Green function (Eq. 36) with potential and the second term corresponding to the multiple scattering including the structural Green function $G_{LL'}^{nn'}(\epsilon)$ as shown in Eq. 42.

3.6 KKR impurity Green function

In real application, it is important to understand the impact of defects in crystal, as the defects can give birth to new properties of materials. Possible defects are distortions in crystal structure or intentionally or naturally occur impurity atoms. In our scenario, we are interested to the intentionally impurity doping. The KKR Green function can be extended to calculate the effect of the impurity in pure host crystal. The modified KKR Green function due to impurity embedded system is referred to as KKR impurity Green function.

Figure 7: Substitution of a Host atom (blue circle) by impurity (red circle): The impurity region (light and transparent green area) will be subject of impurity potential, therefore three type Green Function will be our concern. (i) Green Function in host area, (ii) Green function in impurity area, (iii) Green Function in impurity to host area.

When a host site of potential V_{host}^n is replaced by an impurity of potential

V_{imp}^n . The t-matrix for the impurity atom can be obtained by utilising Eq. 25. In this substitution process, the effect of potential difference due to embedding impurity will exist in finite region around the impurity. The structural green function for impurity is defined in the impurity region and obtained by Dyson equation (Eq. 24) as

$$G_{imp,LL'}^{nn'} = G_{host,LL'}^{nn'} + \sum_{n'',L'',L'''} G_{host,LL''}^{nn''} \Delta t_{L''L'''}^{n''} G_{imp,L''L'}^{n''n'} \quad (44)$$

where n, n', n'' belong to the impurity region and $\Delta t^{n''} = t_{imp}^{n''} - t_{host}^{n''}$. Therefore, $\Delta t^{n''}$ equals to zero outside the impurity region and exist only inside the impurity area. The KKR impurity embedding calculation can be summarized in the following steps

- (i) Construct host Green function $G_{host}^{nn'}(\epsilon)$ for impurity region
- (ii) Calculate t-matrix t_{host}^n for host atoms in impurity region
- (iii) Choose input potential V_{in} and calculate t-matrix t_{imp}^n for all atoms in impurity region
- (iv) Obtain Δt matrix from the t-matrices in (ii) and (iii)
- (v) Calculate structural Green function $G_{imp}^{nn'}(\epsilon)$ and corresponding Green function $G^{nn'}(r, r', \epsilon)$ for impurity region
- (vi) Calculate charge density ρ from Green function, then output potential V_{out} from Poisson equation
- (vii) Mix output potential V_{out} and input potential V_{in}
- (viii) Check V_{mix} and V_{in} if not converged then continue from (iii) by setting V_{mix} to V_{in}

4 Atomistic Model of Magnetism

In this chapter, we will render a general picture of the classical atomistic Heisenberg model for magnetism¹⁰. With this model, we discuss different magnetic energy terms on a length scale of lattice constant. The classical Heisenberg model considers the magnetic moments as of fixed length and assumed not to be changed upon rotation. The magnetic moment of an atom includes the contributions from the angular momentum of all electrons around the nucleus (comparatively small and negligible) and the spin magnetic moments of all electrons (main part of the magnetic moment). In an atomistic model, atomic magnetic moments in the lattice interact with each other as well as external field in a various ways. The interactions evolve various energy terms as

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Z + \mathcal{H}_{DDI} + \mathcal{H}_{EX} + \mathcal{H}_{DMI} + \mathcal{H}_S \quad (45)$$

Where

- (i) Zeeman energy (\mathcal{H}_Z) comes from interaction between external field and lattice magnetic moment. The Zeeman energy of the a crystal due to the external magnetic field \vec{B} is written as

$$\mathcal{H}_Z = \sum_i \vec{B} \cdot \vec{m}_i \quad (46)$$

- (ii) dipole-dipole interaction energy (\mathcal{H}_{DDI}) comes from the interaction of point dipoles. In this scenario, atomic magnetic moments are considered as separated point dipoles. It is long-range interaction and the interaction between two magnetic moments is analogous to the interaction between two magnetostatic dipoles. For a sufficiently small system, the energy can be neglected compared to the Heisenberg exchange interaction. The total dipole-dipole interaction energy over the crystal

$$\mathcal{H}_{DDI} = -\frac{\mu_0}{8\pi} \sum_{i \neq j} \frac{3 \left(\vec{m}_i \cdot \hat{r}_{ij} \right) \left(\vec{m}_j \cdot \hat{r}_{ij} \right) - \vec{m}_i \cdot \vec{m}_j}{r_{ij}^3} \quad (47)$$

- (iii) Heisenberg exchange interaction energy (\mathcal{H}_{EX}) is a form of isotropic interaction between the two magnetic atoms. This is short-range interaction and in short range consideration the \mathcal{H}_{EX} dominates on the \mathcal{H}_{DDI} . Among all the magnetic energy term \mathcal{H}_{EX} is the largest one. In our work, we are mainly interested on the Heisenberg interaction leading the \mathcal{H}_{EX} energy. The Heisenberg exchange interaction energy is

$$\mathcal{H}_{EX} = - \sum_{j>i} J_{ij} (\vec{m}_i \cdot \vec{m}_j) \quad (48)$$

¹⁰In this section we will mainly follow the lecture note *Atomistic and Micromagnetic models of magnetism* by N.S.Kiselev, B. Zimmermann and J.Chico. [62]

- (iv) Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction energy (\mathcal{H}_{DMI}) from the anti-symmetric interaction between the two magnetic moments. The interaction energy is highly dependent on the crystal symmetry. For instance, the interaction energy tends to zero for fcc bcc and simple cubic lattices. This is another important term in our concern. The energy in mathematical form is represented as

$$\mathcal{H}_{DMI} = - \sum_{j>i} \vec{D}_{ij} \cdot (\vec{m}_i \times \vec{m}_j) \quad (49)$$

- (v) The final term forms magnetocrystalline anisotropic interaction. The interaction type could be uniaxial anisotropic (interaction along z-axis or on the plane perpendicular to the z-axis) or cubic anisotropic (interaction along the edges or diagonal of the lattice cube). Comparing with Heisenberg exchange interaction energy between two magnetic atomic moments, the anisotropic interaction is weaker [63].

4.1 Extended Heisenberg model

The model consists of isotropic exchange interaction, and anisotropic exchange coupling interaction (anti-symmetric DMI interaction, and traceless symmetric interaction part).

$$\mathcal{H}_H = \mathcal{H}_{EX} + \mathcal{H}_{DMI} + \mathcal{H}_S$$

Here we are not taking account of traceless symmetric part, \mathcal{H}_S , as it is considerably smaller regarding the exchange interaction and the DMI interaction [63].

$$\mathcal{H}_H = - \sum_{j>i} J_{ij} \vec{m}_i \cdot \vec{m}_j - \sum_{j>i} \vec{D}_{ij} \cdot (\vec{m}_i \times \vec{m}_j) \quad (50)$$

The Heisenberg exchange interaction term J_{ij} is the most effective and leading contribution to the collinear interaction energy. The sign of J_{ij} is responsible for magnetic interaction order among the atomic magnetic moments, a positive sign for J_{ij} stands for ferromagnetic interaction and a negative sign indicates antiferromagnetic interaction. In most general scenario J_{ij} is short-range exchange interaction, thus with increasing the inter-distance between sites the value of J_{ij} decreases rapidly. For larger contribution of the RKKY interaction, the J_{ij} oscillate with distance and then the AFM ground state, shown in Fig. 8, will be achievable. For instance, the sign of J_{in} for exchange interaction of the i^{th} site to the sites in n^{th} shell is different than that for next nearest shell ($(n+1)^{\text{th}}$), an stable noncollinear magnetic ground state would be expected. The resultant pattern of the exchange interaction is periodically spiral called *exchange spiral*. The *RKKY* interaction takes place when the nuclear magnetic moment (I) takes part in exchange interaction indirectly with conduction d- or f-electrons of transition elements. As the exchange interaction $J_{ij,ind}$ (indirect

Figure 8: fcc lattice: Consider 001-plane indicating magnetic moments of few atoms. Typical atomic shell around an atom shows that a red atom has 4 atoms (yellow atoms) at the first and second shell (red atoms) each. Thus the center atom isotropically interact with the same atoms in certain shell by equal strength. The interactions explains competitive interactions with opposite sign for different shells. Figure produced by VESTA [5].

exchange interaction between site i and j) indirectly acts between two nuclear magnetic moments (at the sites i and j), thus the interaction is also called *indirect exchange interaction*. For this indirect exchange interaction, the lattice might see competitive interactions in different shells which rise spiral magnetic interaction among the magnetic moments.

The Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction (second term in Eq. 50) contributes to noncollinear interaction as the magnetic moments tend to align by 90° or 270° angle. By perception in Fig. 9, DMI has tensor components. The change of the magnetic moment vector orientation due to DMI interaction leads to DMI in different direction which in turn changes the vector orientation of magnetic moments again. Very often the tensor components of DMI depend on the symmetry of the crystal, and for high symmetric crystals like fcc, bcc and simple cubic $D_{ij} = 0$ [64].

The Heisenberg Eq. 50 can be written in tensor form

$$\mathcal{H}_H = - \sum_{j>i} \vec{m}_i \cdot \mathcal{J}_{ij} \vec{m}_j \quad (51)$$

the tensor \mathcal{J}_{ij} can be resolved into three components.

$$\mathcal{J}_{ij} = J_{ij} \mathbb{1} + \mathcal{J}_{ij}^A + \mathcal{J}_{ij}^S \quad (52)$$

Figure 9: Typical DMI interactions **(a), Left figure:** Magnetic moment displacement on $\{010\}$ planes thus the resultant DMI vector along Y-axis. **(b), Right figure:** Magnetic moment displacement on $[100]$ -plane, then the resultant DMI out of plane.

$\mathbb{1}$ is a unit matrix which refers $J_{ij}^{xx} = J_{ij}^{yy} = J_{ij}^{zz} = \frac{1}{3}J_{ij}$ and

$$\mathcal{J}_{ij}^A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & J_{ij}^{xy} & J_{ij}^{xz} \\ J_{ij}^{yx} & 0 & J_{ij}^{yz} \\ J_{ij}^{zx} & J_{ij}^{zy} & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & J_{ij}^{xy} & -J_{ij}^{zx} \\ -J_{ij}^{xy} & 0 & J_{ij}^{yz} \\ J_{ij}^{zx} & -J_{ij}^{yz} & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -D_{ij}^z & D_{ij}^y \\ D_{ij}^z & 0 & -D_{ij}^x \\ -D_{ij}^y & D_{ij}^x & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We are skipping the anisotropic or traceless symmetric part \mathcal{J}_{ij}^S . For layer structured system the contribution of isotropic interaction J_{ij} and anti-symmetric interaction D_{ij} are larger than the anisotropic traceless symmetric part [63].

4.2 Calculation of \underline{J}_{ij} tensor elements

To calculate the tensor \underline{J}_{ij} , we need to calculate energy variation ΔE_{ij} due to the perturbation taking place at sites i and j . The perturbation arises from the changes of orientation in the spin magnetic moment by infinitesimal rotation in that sites. The energy ΔE_{ij} can be calculated within the multiple scattering framework and combined use of Lloyd's formula as follows [65] [66]. The energy change calculated with Green function is written as

$$\Delta E_{ij} = \frac{-1}{\pi} \text{Im} \left\{ \int dE \text{Tr} \Delta t^i G^{ij} \Delta t^j G^{ji} \right\} \quad (53)$$

The Green function G^{ji} is described by $G^{ij}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}'; \epsilon)$ as discussed in Eq. 43.

The variation in t-matrix Δt^i due to the potential variation in site i is obtained from the equation as

$$\Delta t^i = \int dr R_L^i \Delta V^i(\vec{r}) R_{L'}^i = \Delta V_{L,L'}^i$$

With different orientations of the spin momentum at site i and j the components of ΔE^{ij} correspond to the exchange coupling tensor components of the $\underline{\underline{J}}_{ij}$ and can be written as

$$J_{ij}^{\beta_i \beta_j} = -\frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} \left\{ \int dE \text{Tr} \Delta V_{LL'}^{\beta_i} G^{ij} \Delta V_{LL'}^{\beta_j} G^{ji} \right\} \quad (54)$$

Here, the $\beta_{i(j)}$ stands for spin momentum polarisation at site $i(j)$ and is expressed by Pauli spins $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$. After separating the tensor proponents in Eq. 54 into different parts, the exchange coupling Heisenberg Hamiltonian is given by

$$H_{ex} = -\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sum_{ij} \vec{m}_i J_{ij} \vec{m}_j + \sum_{ij} \vec{m}_i \underline{\underline{J}}_{ij}^s \vec{m}_j + \sum_{ij} \vec{D}_{ij} [\vec{m}_i \times \vec{m}_j] \right\}$$

Here J_{ij} is the isotropic exchange coupling diagonal matrix, $\underline{\underline{J}}_{ij}^s$ is the traceless symmetric part of the tensor $\underline{\underline{J}}_{ij}$ and the final term is the anti symmetric part.

5 A Scalable Computational Infrastructure with AiiDA

In present years, the design based on the simulation driven techniques has become increasingly important in the realm of materials science. The data driven condensed matter research fields are being fueled by unprecedented development of super-computing resources [9]. Apart from the availability of the huge amount of crystal structure data [67, 68, 69, 70], fully integrated frameworks of tools and database facilitate high throughput investigation. Nowadays, great amount of high throughput calculations are being performed using density functional theory based codes [71, 72, 73].

Data is crucial part of the modern civilization. In the perspective of material research, data-driven material development is a new paradigm and is considered as a fourth scientific revolution followed by Theoretical, experimental and simulation aspect [74]. With the immense amount of material data, this paradigm accelerate the improvement of the existing material as well as discovers new materials with expected properties. Though the reliable data come from the collaboration among theories, simulations and experiments, but the data driven tools like AI and machine learning process the data with different established models. The process of the data can unravel the secret co-relation which helps to develop tools to anticipate the material properties. In 1997 such an data based computational experiment had been conducted by the researchers of Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) to predict the interaction voltage of cathode in Li-batterie [75].

The high-throughput kind simulation might be one of the great sources for data. To accelerated the data-based material science the material research community emphasize on the development of software keeping mind of several important facts. Some facts are associated with data model and data infrastructure. For example, the efficient data query method which will reduce the data query time [6], efficiency of storage size [6], reproducibility by storing data provenance [76, 77, 78, 79], easy data shearing scheme [6, 80]. It is also important to make the software user and developer friendly. Which requires the feasibility to tackle the lager number of calculations at the same time, flexibility in integration to other existing computational software [6] and flexibility in design of automated workflows [6]. Regarding such required facts AiiDA is one of the modern simulation softwares in computational material science. There are some others tools Fireworks [31], AFLOW [81], GC3Pie [34], Signac [82] to design executable workflows (in parallel) via Python language. But unlike the others, AiiDA facilitate the data provenance details by storing the inter-connection among input data, calculation and output data. Such provenance continues recursively until data are being used to any child process. The AiiDA framework combines an automation engine, python API easy to use as well as database storage. The engine is responsible for submitting calculation to the computing resources(local or remote through SSH) and for running AiiDA computational task. AiiDA has build-in support for well known job scheduler to communicate with

computing resource. It provides customised language provided by AiiDA's core API through Python programming Language. To construct the calculations and workflows the usage of the customised language is an important tools. The data in the rationale database can be searched and accessed by Python API. AiiDA stores data or contents of the provenance graph as files in repository or in tables in a database. The Object Relational Mapper (ORM) either Django¹¹ or SQLAlchemy¹² can be used to query the data on the provenance graph through Python API. A metaphoric provenance graph is represented in Figure-11 for summation between the two integer numbers. In this metaphorical example, data query on the provenance graph allows any traversal among the AiiDA nodes¹³. By this manner provenance graph can include further predecessor and successor calculation nodes until they are exist.

The AiiDA ontology enables the users to extend the AiiDA core functionality for developing the plugins. The AiiDA provides flexible plugin system to interact with the external simulation codes, to add customised input and output data types and parser. The *AiiDA-KKR* plugin has been developed with this AiiDA plugin system.

5.1 AiiDA Architecture

AiiDA is mainly developed to enhance the workflow design which enables to run highly complex high-throughput computational tasks. AiiDA also provides fully automatic provenance and supports for high-performance computing resources. The core architecture of AiiDA is shown in Fig. 10

Figure 10: An Schematic overview of AiiDA Architecture showing different fundamental section. Source: [6].

¹¹<https://www.djangoproject.com/>

¹²<https://www.sqlalchemy.org/>

¹³Process node e.g. WorkChainNode, CalcJobNode and data node e.g. Int, Float are some AiiDA nodes. For more details of AiiDA data node: <https://aiida.readthedocs.io/projects/aiida-core/en/v1.6.3/topics/data.types.html>

5.1.1 Engine

The engine of AiiDA runs the calculations and workflows in parallel supervised by the daemon runners. Daemon monitors and relaunches the calculation in case it is needed. AiiDA engine enables the AiiDA to run tens of thousands of concurrent tasks together in different computing resources [6]. This large amount of concurrent tasks are handled by daemon runners independently but reserving the hierarchy task and workflow. During the execution of the computational task via AiiDA engine, AiiDA stores the process and data connections in provenance graph. AiiDA engine mainly implements three core concepts process, calculation, and workflow.

A Process is an entity that execute codes with given input and produce output. Each process is run by AiiDA engine. There are two flavours of processes: Calculations and workflows. A calculation is a process that creates new data by executing some code snippet or large calculation and generate output data. A typical example of calculation is execution of the external codes to the remote computing resources or local computer. Another flavour is workflow which run some other calculations and other workflows or sub-workflows. Thus, workflows do not generate any any data directly rather return or store data from other nested calculations. The simple way to define calculation or workflow process is to use the python decorator¹⁴ *@calcfunction* or *@workflowfunction* at the leading line of a python function, respectively. These AiiDA's defined syntax tell to the AiiDA runners to store the inputs and outputs of calculations as well as nested calculations and sub-workflows in workflows. To store the data and their corresponding links we use provenance graph. In material simulation, the *CalcJob* is adapted with the external codes via the plugins. The plugin helps to pre-define the input and output AiiDA datatypes. As workflow runs the nested calculations and other sub-workflows AiiDA plugin system for workflow also give advantage for input and output AiiDA datatypes. Once a process e.g. *CalcJob* is submitted, the engine takes the control over the process, performs all the steps for completion the calculation.

5.1.2 Provenance graph model

AiiDA provenance graph can be considered as directed acyclic graph (DAG) where each vertices represent AiiDA data node. The edges between the two nodes is called link. The link can be used to find a node with incoming and outgoing link from a specified node. The node types are the process node and data node. The process node consists the AiiDA processes *CalculationNode* and *WorkflowNode*. The data nodes group include *Integer*, *Float*, *Dict*, *ArrayData* and other computational datatype converting to the AiiDA datatype. Link type is also another important component of the provenance graph. Link indicates the inter-connection between two linking nodes. For instance, *INPUT_CALC* and *INPUT_WORK* represent the data node to process

¹⁴Python decorator is a functional method that takes another function as an argument and return that function after explicitly extension of behavior of the given.

Figure 11: A schematic provenance graph for multiply *CalcJob* calculation: With two input *Int* nodes the *CalcJob* returns one *Int* output node by accomplishing the successful multiply calculations. Distinctly, the rectangle symbols the process and the ellipse symbols the data nodes (green color). Each node is identified with the unique universal ID (inside the brackets). Source: [7]

node. The links *CALL_CALC* and *CALL_WORK* are the type used to refer the called process.

5.1.3 Database abstraction and querying language

For a high-throughput research project like Design of Magnetic Interactions in Doped Topological Insulators the provenance graph might contain millions of process and data nodes. For efficient traversal in provenance graph, tools are needed. For efficient performant tools, AiiDA uses relational database and store the provenance graph. Where the nodes in provenance graph also include node data properties and extend the power of query data tool. The present database solution for AiiDA is PostgreSQL using SQL language. Though the SQL language is efficient but needs long and cumbersome query writing. AiiDA does not write SQL query but depends on object-relational mapping (ORM) like Django and SQLAlchemy. To reduce the query effort as much as possible without compromise with efficiency, AiiDA *QueryBuilder* tool via Python interface gives an abstract form of the query process as simple as possible. For instance, in high-throughput calculation it is a very usual case finishing a large number of *CalcJob* or *WorkChain* with error which returns non-zero value. To find and remove them one can use AiiDA *QueryBuilder*. For example the code snippet 1 finds all the *WorkflowNodes* and the nodes having process *pk* or *id* greater than 57959. The nodes will be filtered according to *process_label* and *exit_status* attribute together by *and* key.

Code Snippet 1:

```
from aiida.orm import QueryBuilder
qb = QueryBuilder()
Qb_node_list = qbl.append(WorkChainNode,
    filters={
        'and':[
            {'attributes.process_label':'kkr_imp_wc'},
            {'attributes.exit_status':{'!in':[0]}}
        ],
        'id':{'>':57959},
    }
).all()
```

This code snippet returns a list of *WorkChainNodes* and each *WorkChainNode* satisfies the attributes and properties added by parameter filters. Thus, the nodes of the list are the failed *kkr_imp_wc* *WorkChainNode* with id greater than 57959.

6 The AiiDA-KKR Plugin and Its Application

Till now a general overview about the AiiDA infrastructure and KKR Green function method have been discussed in a small extend, where the KKR Green function method is the underlining theory for JuKKR code¹⁵ package. The JuKKR code package consists of three different codes Voronoi, KKRhost and KKRimp. To run high throughput calculation via JuKKR code group, AiiDA-KKR plugin¹⁶ has been developed utilising the high performance advantages of AiiDA [9]. By taking facilities provided by AiiDA, AiiDA-KKR plugins allows to accelerate the high-throughput calculations deducing user interactions and declining no-frills human errors for complex calculations. With the advantage of AiiDA database and data model, e.g. data provenance, in future AiiDA-KKR plugin would add an effort for the realm data based material research.

In this chapter we will discuss the different sub-plugins (Calculation Plugins and workflows plugins) and other characteristics AiiDA-KKR tools. As an example of workflows, the Band structure workflows and its corresponding result will be discussed. In this thesis the central focus to the work of the development of the Band-structure workflow (*kkr_bs_wc*) and more importantly a combine-impurity workflow (*combineimps_wc*). The combine-impurity workflow enables embedding the multiple impurities into a host crystal which also gives access to physical properties like magnetic interaction. To have a look on detail descriptions of the input and output data nodes and structure of individual workflow and calculation its online documentation is useful¹⁷.

Our AiiDA-KKR plugins are efficient enough to perform ab initio calculation, Band structure calculation and impurity embedding calculation to a large extent by exploiting the codes from the JuKKR code package.

6.1 Calculations plugins

Every calculation plugin builds on code specific input AiiDA data objects (e.g. *StructureData*, *Dict*) and a parser to parse retrieve output files into AiiDA data objects. The *Calculation* plugins¹⁸ consist of three plugins, *VoronoiCalculation* plugin, *KkrCalculation* plugin and *KkrimpCalculation* plugin. It is noteworthy to introduce the three calculations plugins: (1) *VoronoiCalculation* constructs the shape functions [83, 84] required for full potentials treatment and starting potential of crystal cluster, (2) *KkrCalculation* allows to perform the self-consistency (scf), Density of States (DOS), Band-Structure(BS) and host Green Function calculation and (3) *KkrimpCalculation* allows to construct the impurity cluster potential and perform calculation for magnetic interaction between the magnetic dopants. Each calculation requires input nodes as well as

¹⁵<https://iffgit.fz-juelich.de/kkr/jukkr>

¹⁶<https://github.com/JuDFTteam/aaida-kkr>

¹⁷<https://aiida-kkr.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹⁸https://github.com/JuDFTteam/aaida-kkr/tree/develop/aaida_kkr/calculations

Figure 12: *VoronoiCalculation*: The crystal structure, pre-compiled code and calculation parameters are the required inputs for *VoronoiCalculation*. The output *RemoteData* contain crystal shape function and starting potential required for the *KkrCalculation*. The output parameters *Dict* returns info of calculation e.g. code version, compiler info, cluster etc

returns the output nodes where some of the nodes are optional¹⁹. For instance *VoronoiCalculation* needs input parameters *Dict* node, *Voronoi Code*, *StructureData* node as mandatory inputs (Figure 12). After finishing successfully, the *VoronoiCalculation* returns output parameters *Dict* node by parsing the data of intended result as well as *RemoteData* node containing crystal shape function and starting potential. The action of storing data nodes of the entire process with their directed connection are done by the AiiDA Daemon.

6.2 Workflow plugins

In addition to the Calculations plugins AiiDA-KKR package also has Workflow plugins²⁰ which consist of some several workflows. Each workflow is the inclusion of Calculation plugins and in some situation of the other workflows or sub-workflows plugins in nested steps. Thus the basic construction of the workflows to bundle all the calculations, sub-workflows and other necessary steps into a python module. This simple way helps to track all the calculation and their corresponding input and output nodes associated with the workflow for any specific interest in physics. Such an attempt also fascinate pre-automation of the some inputs parameters value which reduces the unwanted user interaction and no-frill human error. An example is the *kkr_bs_wc* (BandStructure) workflow and Fig. 13 explains an arrangement of a typical *kkr_bs_wc* workflow

¹⁹For any calculation or workflow plugin AiiDA accepts and returns only AiiDA data nodes (e.g. *StructureData*, *Code*, *Dict*, *RemoteData*, *FolderData*)

²⁰https://github.com/JuDFTteam/aaida-kkr/tree/develop/aiida_kkr/workflows

submission. In this typical example, beside the three required inputs it also needs k-point data node (*KpointsData* node not shown in figure). The k-point data is extracted from the input *StructureData* node internally if not explicitly given. After finishing the *KkrCalculation*, the band structure data is parsed to the *ArrayData* node. The *BS_data* node has all the information like k-points data with corresponding label, energy points and density of states.

Figure 13: Band structure workflow Combine three steps: (i) Validating the least mandatory inputs i.e *RemoteData* form the parent calculation, input parameters *Dict* and *KKR Code* (ii) running the band structure calculation step by returning the *FolderData*, and output parameters *Dict*. (iii) in final step the band structure data is parsed to the *ArrayData*

The development of the workflow *combineimps_wc* for combination of impurities and its application is the major part of this thesis. Fig. 14 gives graphical representation of *combineimps_wc* construction. The *Calcfuction create_combined_imp_info_cf* of *combineimps_wc* adds two converged impurity cluster from two successfully converged *kkr_imp_wc* workflows (step *Create-big-cluster* in flowchart Fig. 14). Where each single impurity cluster comes either from single impurity calculation *KkrimpCalculation* or single impurity *kkr_imp_wc* workflow or single impurity *kkr_imp_sub_wc*. On later step the workflow checks for host Green function of required size and the same parent host structure. If the Green function is not provided the the Green function would be writeout in *host_gf_writeout* step.

After finishing the Combination of the impurity clusters, validation for host Green function, construction of the big potential and crystal convergence step with *KkrimpCalculation*, the workflow reach to the end step if no special run option is given. However, in *combineimps_wc* workflow we implemented a calculation step $J_{i,j}$ Heisenberg interaction by activating the run option *jij-run* to true. The workflow returns *workflow_info Dict* (contains the cluster data, code version, etc) , *last_calc_output_parameters Dict* (contains the calculation output of the last calculation of self-consistency step), *last_potential SingleFileData* (crystal potential of the last calculation step), *last_calc_remote RemoteData*(contains the info of the calculation running folder).

Figure 14: Flowchart for *combine_imp_wc* showing workflow plan.

6.3 Tools

Apart from the Workflow plugins and Calculation plugins, the AiiDA-KKR plugin has also a useful module called *Tools*²¹. Two very frequently used tools are *kktparams* and *plot_kkr*. The *kktparams* facilitate to set the single and multiple parameters and corresponding values for input data *Dict*. The *plot_kkr* provides the plot of the crystal structures, density of states (DOS), band structure from calculation or workflows identity number²².

Taking advantage of the automation plotting function *plot_kkr*, we have investigated the band structure of Bi_2Te_3 in bulk region with different spin-orbit coupling (SOC) (in Fig. 15). Which represents, how spin orbit coupling dominates band gap of quantum spin hall topological insulators.

²¹https://github.com/JuDFTteam/aiida-kkr/tree/develop/aiida_kkr/tools

²²In AiiDA identity number is represented by `pk(integer)`, `uuid(string)` or universally unique identifier like label. The value of integer 'pk' can be varied from the database to database but the string 'uuid' always unique irrespective of database or machine.

Figure 15: Band structure plot for different SOC interactions.

7 Magnetic Impurity Analysis in TI

In real materials imperfections and impurities are unavoidable and they come naturally. Sometimes intentionally doped impurities may permit to realize fascinating new physical properties. An interesting example of the impurity doping are magnetic defects in topological insulators (TI), responsible for quantum anomalous Hall state of matter. This Quantum Anomalous Hall (QAH) state opens a new venue for the development of low power electronics, spintronics and quantum computation. Nowadays, the role of the magnetic impurities in TIs is an important part of topological based material research and design [9].

In this section, we will investigate the impact of the magnetic impurity in a well-known topological insulator Bi_2Te_3 in terms of the QAHE. Moreover, the material class Sb_2Te_3 and Bi_2Se_3 or $(\text{Bi}, \text{Sb})_2(\text{SeTe})_3$'s alloys promise to show some outstanding properties such as the tunability of the Dirac point [85] and transport properties in the presence of defects [86] and with doping [87]. In experiments the QAH state was realized by doping $(\text{Bi}, \text{Sb})_2\text{Te}_3$ with 3d transition elements Cr and V which shows the QAHE and stable Dirac gap in the topological surface states [11, 10] under suitable physical circumstances. The difficulties for stable QAH state are our motivations to study different magnetic dopants for more stable QAH.

For achieving stable QAHE, some favourable conditions are low densities of bulk carriers, long-range ferromagnetic (FM) order directing out of plane and very low temperature ($< 100\text{mK}$) [9]. Another attempt for stable and large Dirac gap in the TI is to use the rare earth (RE) elements benefited from their large magnetic moment [88, 89, 90]. Recently, anti-ferromagnetic (AFM) order opens a new venue with successful anti-ferromagnetic topology insulator MnBi_2Te_4 [91, 92].

In this thesis we study 3d and 4d impurities in the prototypical TI Bi_2Te_3 . This work is mainly intended to investigate magnetic momentum of different positional setup or configuration of the impurity atoms of d-block elements. Besides the magnitude of the magnetic moment, the magnetic exchange coupling between the impurities is also our matter of concern. As the alignment of the magnetic impurity and their magnetic moment vector direction play also important roles for the stable QAHE. Collectively strong magnetic moment out of plane of surface is needed for QAH state, but the non-collinear interaction can arise from DMI which opposes the magnetic collinear alignment. Finally, we will endeavour to understand how the correlation among the magnetic moments explain the stability of possible QAH systems.

7.1 Computational setup

For this work, the alloy Bi_2Te_3 serves as base crystal and the unit cell used in simulation shown in (Fig. 16, left). Fundamentally, the material consists of quintuple layers (Fig. 16, right) and attached by van der Waals (vdW) force between quintuple layers. Because of the weakly inter-quintuple layer bound the layers are considerably apart. In the KKR method, space is divided into

cells centered around the atoms, which requires insertion of additional so called empty sphere into the unit cell. These spurious atoms do not contain any charges or nucleus and only fill up the empty space. To include the correct

Figure 16: Host crystal structure construct with `plot_kkr` from AiiDA-KKR tools [8]. **Left:** Unit cell used in simulation with primitive lattice vectors $\mathbf{a}=(2.19, 3.80, 0.0)\text{\AA}$, $\mathbf{b}=(-2.19, 3.80, 0.0)\text{\AA}$ and $\mathbf{c}=(0, -2.53, 10.16)\text{\AA}$. Empty sphere in between the atom layers that are needed for technical reason in the KKR method are omitted. **Right:** Visualisation of quintuple layers in (001) planes for modified structure for the sake of visibility. Te and Bi atoms are shown in golden and violet colors, respectively. The Te (Te1, Te2, Te3) and Bi (Bi1, Bi2) atoms are ascending numbered from top side to the bottom side of the left figure. The van der Waals gap is located in between Te2 and Te3.

charge screening of the impurity atom, a certain size of the impurity centered cluster needs to contain some shells of neighboring host atoms. We choose $R_{cut} = 7.01 \text{ \AA}$ as radius of the spherical impurity cluster. An typical cluster centering a Tellurium (Te) atom have 6-Bi, 6-Te, 6-Te, 6-Bi, 6-Te and 2-Te atoms on neighbouring shells located at distances 3.24\AA , 4.38\AA , 4.48\AA , 5.45\AA , 6.27\AA , and 6.99\AA respectively.

During the convergence of the self-consistent field iterations for the impurity embedding, we used hybrid version of the `Jukkr`²³ code which includes both MPI and OpenMP parallel computing scheme. In the convergence step, we set cut-off angular momentum $l_{cut} = 3$ (discussed in Eq.39) and the corresponding truncation error has been corrected by using Lloyd’s formula [93]. Furthermore, we have used LDA (local density approximation) exchange correlation functional and SOC has been included self-consistently in the calculations.

For further comparison the results from the interaction of impurities, we run calculation with the coherent potential approximation (CPA). The CPA is an alternative approach to describe the disorder.

In this work we use host-impurity notation as follows: The symbols I_H ²⁴

²³<https://iffgit.fz-juelich.de/kkr/jukkr>

²⁴Careful H and I do not interpret the elements Hydrogen and Iodine

stands that the host atom H is kicked out from the host crystal by an impurity atom I.

7.2 Density of states in crystalline Bi_2Te_3

To understand the intrinsic property of the impurities in the Bi_2Te_3 alloy, study of the host crystal is important. Density of states (DOS)²⁵ of host gives the intuition of the insulating state in host alloy.

Figure 17: DOS for bulk Bi_2Te_3 . DOS for all host atoms excluding the empty spheres.

The DOS (Fig. 17) for the bulk Bi_2Te_3 shows that for the energies below Fermi level the Te atoms have dominance in DOS over the Bi atoms. Distinctively, the atom *Te1* (Te atom at top most of unit cell in Fig. 16) has larger density of states relative to the other elements (*Te2* and *Te3*) of the same group. It is because *Te1* (on the upper plane of the unit cell Fig. 16) is located in the center of the quintuple layer and has two nearest Bi layers which also contribute states to the *Te1* atom due to the covalent bonds between the atoms. The other two Te atoms terminate the quintuple layer to the vdW gap and each Te has only one Bi layer at nearest vicinity, show the same electronic DOS pattern. Similarly, each Bi atom has also two Te atoms next to it therefore contribute same electronic DOS curve.

²⁵The density of the electronic states is the number of states (for spin up and spin down), per unit volume and per energy unit at a specific energy level, that allow electrons to occupy.

Regarding DOS above the Fermi level, Bi atom has a larger value compared to Te constituents. This large DOS contribution from Bi comes from the half-filled p-orbitals which allows larger availability states. Importantly, around the Fermi energy level the global minimum DOS approaches to zero ensures the insulating states in the bulk region as expected for this atomic system. The electronic band structure (only one direction) of the Bi_2Te_3 with full spin-orbit coupling (most right of Fig. 15) predict large band gap (approximately 400meV) in the bulk region.

7.3 DOS for d-block transitional elements in Bi_2Te_3

In this part, we will study density of states (DOS) of the transition elements from single impurity calculation with Bi_2Te_3 host. For realising a stable QAHE, a key condition is low density of states in bulk region of impurity crystal[9]. In Fig. 18(a) shows the elements Nb has peak DOS at the Fermi energy level (resonance in Fermi level) and others have peak DOS either left (e.g. Co, V) or right (e.g. Rh, Cr) of the Fermi level. The elements with peak DOS left or right of Fermi level have relatively less DOS at Fermi energy and other side of Fermi line. The elements in resonance with Fermi level give conducting states for the bulk region. The DOS in Fermi level (Fig. 18(a)), show the 3d and 4d elements as impurity substituting atoms Bi at *Bi1* layer. Here we are paying attention on DOS for 20 d-block elements (3d and 4d) that also consists of transitional metals.

The Impurity kinds Fe, Co from the 3d-transition elements and the kinds Nb, Pd from the 4d-transition elements response with large DOS around the Fermi level (Fig. 18(a)). Some elements (e.g. Ru) have peaks of DOS on the both side of Fermi level. This distinguishable behavior arise from the splitting of the degeneracy states from d-orbital due to the crystal field effect and d-shell filling rules (Hund's rule and Full-Full, Half-Full and Half-Half filling rule of s and d orbital). The bond free electron pairs from the Te split the degenerate states of the d-orbitals ($d_{xy}, d_{yz}, d_{zx}, d_{z^2}, d_{x^2-z^2}$) into two groups e_g and t_{2g} with 2 and 3 orbitals respectively. The splitting of the d-orbitals shifts the orbitals in lower and higher energy orbitals groups and energy separation create the DOS peaks in different energy points around the Fermi level (Fig. 18(a)). A different case is the element Pd which has DOS peak at the Fermi line. The Pd has the full-filled d-orbital thus no crystal effect but has empty 5s orbital contributing the DOS at the Fermi level. The lower DOS at Fermi level can be predicted by the minimum d-orbital energy for example Mn($[\text{Ar}]3s^23d^5$, Full-Half filling), Mo($[\text{Kr}]4s^14d^5$, Half-Half filling), Zn($[\text{Ar}]3s^23d^{10}$ Full-Full filling) are in the minimum energy states.

For long-sought QAH state our observation is restricted to the lower values of the density of states. The V and Cr-doped $(\text{Bi},\text{Sb})_2\text{Te}_3$ [11, 10] are experimentally established unambiguous property of stable QAH state. Considering the DOS around the atoms V and Cr as benchmark value, we observe the DOS for Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, Y, Zr, Mo, Tc, Ru, Rh, Ag and Cd lie on the boundary DOS (2.6 states per eV) or below that value, that satisfies one required key

(a)

(b)

Figure 18: **(a)** Spin integrated DOS of some 3d and 4d elements around Fermi level. **(b)** DOS at the Fermi level of d-block elements: Comparing with the benchmark elements Cr and V (limiting the DOS at Fermi level to 2.6 states per eV), the interested elements with the low density of states are Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, Y, Zr, Mo, Tc, Ru, Rh, Ag and Cd, where some are magnetic and some are not.

factor for stable QAH state (Fig. 18(b)).

7.4 Single impurity magnetic moment

Before moving to the further discussion for clusters containing multiple magnetic impurities, we will study magnetic moment from the single impurity calculations. A large magnetic moment is the another key factor to get long-sought and perpetual QAH effect from the QSHE. In our simulation we fix the orientation of the magnetic moments along the z -axis. We are particularly interested in elements that show equivalent or larger magnetic moments than V or Cr. But, other elements with magnetic moment around $1\mu_B$ or larger might be interesting. As due to the second impurity of larger magnetic moment the first impurity of the smaller moment perceives higher magnetic field which is $\vec{B} = \vec{\sigma} \cdot \vec{m}_2$. The larger effective magnetic field grants larger J_{ij} interaction.

To illustrate the magnetic moments of the transitional metals the electronic configuration in d- or f-orbitals plays fundamental role. The Fig. 19 shows how the magnetic moment follows the electron filling of the d-orbital. Both the 3d and 4d transition metal elements have the same pattern like half sine function. The pattern is expected from the d-orbital filling by Hunds' rule. So, with the increasing number of unpaired spins in d-orbitals the magnetic moment increases and the moment decreases with growing numbers of filled d-orbitals ($d_{xy}, d_{yz}, d_{zx}, d_{z^2}, d_{x^2-y^2}$) by spin-up and -down pairs. We see that elements Cr, V, Mn, Fe, Co, Nb, Mo and Tc are good in agreement with the corresponding value of $1\mu_B$ or larger. Comparing with the selected elements (Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, Y, Zr, Mo, Tc, Ru, Rh, Ag and Cd) from DOS analysis and magnetic moment, we can speculate that Mn, Mo, and Tc are the suitable elements for stable QAH state along with V and Cr. In the following discussions, we will scrutinize this hypothesis with the study of the magnetic interactions between pairs of impurities.

(a)

(b)

Figure 19: **(a)** Spin magnetic moments in unit of Bohr magneton (μ_B) for 3d and 4d transition metals embedded in host Bi_2Te_3 . The impurities with magnetic moments approximately $1\mu_B$, shown by red line, or larger are in our concern. **(b)** Hund's rule for d-orbital electron filling. The larger number of unpaired electron response to the larger magnetic moment, for instance, Mn has largest magnetic moment.

7.5 Magnetic exchange coupling for double impurity calculations

The QAH phase requires multiple impurities in doped TI giving strong ferromagnetic J_{ij} interaction. Thus we need to study multiple magnetic impurities in TI and how the impurities interact with each other. The interactions among the magnetic impurities lead to the total magnetic moment. The presence of the nearby impurities can change the charge transfer of the existing impurities, therefore the d-filling and the magnetic moments. The presence of multi-impurities also induces noncollinear interaction DMI which might be stronger compared to the J_{ij} .

In this section, we are concerned with double impurity calculations and will discuss (i) the resultant magnetic moments of the impurities and their changes due to exchange interaction, (ii) the sign of J_{ij} that indicates either ferromagnetic (FM) or antiferromagnetic (AFM) interaction order, (iii) the competition of J_{ij} and DMI to determine the collinearity.

Figure 21: The figure shows the changes in magnetic moment, along x-axis, of first impurity atoms doped in the Bi layer (Bi1 atomic layer). The changes take place due to the insertion of the second impurity in next nearest neighbour cell and on the same Bi quintuple layer. The data in first column for symbol X represents the differences in magnetic moment without any insertion of the second impurity and therefore differences are be zero. The calculated Spin magnetic momentum are in the z-axis.

total magnetic moment in pairs.

Fig.21 gives fine differences in the magnetic moments of the first impurity. The differences occur due to the substitutional insertion of the second impurity in the next neighboring unit cell in the same plane. Elements of 4d-transition metals are more sensitive compare to the 3d-transition metals. This behavior is predictable, as the balance shell electrons of 4d-transition metals are loosely bound to the atom. The loosely bound electrons are ready to respond to the nearer magnetic moments. The electrons can be sensible either in ferromagnetic or anti-ferromagnetic order to the nearer atomic magnetic moment. Thus, the higher magnetic susceptibility of the balance shell electrons leads to the relatively larger changes of the magnetic moment in the first impurity atoms.

7.5.2 Magnetic exchange interaction for a finite distance

For multi-impurity systems, the Heisenberg exchange interaction J_{ij} and the Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction (DMI) are important physical terms to understand the perpetuity of magnetic order and magnetic collinearity. In Fig. 9, we realize that DMI favors the alignment of magnetic moments in noncollinear configurations. Thus DMI opposes J_{ij} favoring collinear arrangement of magnetic moments. In our work, we are motivated to find a good approximation for strong ferromagnetic interaction order and weak DMI for the stable and long-sought QAH state. The figures Fig. 22 and Fig. 23 represent the Heisenberg exchange interaction and DMI interaction in a couple of two magnetic impurities respectively.

Figure 22: Heisenberg spin interaction, J_{ij} (in unit of meV) between magnetic moments of two impurity atoms i and j . The impurity pairs are corresponds to the impurity arrangement as Fig. 21. The red and blue colors represent ferromagnetic and anti-ferromagnetic interaction respectively.

It seems impossible to render a general scaling behavior of Heisenberg exchange interaction J_{ij} by only considering the atomic numbers of the d-block elements. Regarding the main diagonal data of Heisenberg exchange interaction (Fig. 22), most of the elements which do not belong to any electrons pair (spin up and spin down) in their magnetic d-orbitals interact in ferromagnetic order. For example, V, Cr, Ti, Nb, Mo, Ru each does not contain any paired electrons in their balance shell's d-orbitals. The lion shear of elements having

Figure 23: Magnitude of anisotropic exchange interaction vector DMI, between the magnetic impurities arranged as same as arranged in Fig 20.

at least one or more paired electrons (spin up and spin down) in their balance shell's d-orbitals interact in anti-ferromagnetic order. Moreover, the elements Cr and V strengthen ferromagnetic interaction with other ferromagnetic type elements compared to the interactions in mono-doped crystal. For example, Cr-Cr and Mo-Mo interactions give approximately 12 meV and 7.8 meV respectively, while Cr-Mo interaction gives 18 meV. In another way, the kinds Mn, Fe, and Co enhance the anti-ferromagnetic interaction compared to anti-ferromagnetic interaction in mono-doped crystals. For instance, Co-Co and Tc-Tc interact by energy -17 meV and -0.72 meV, while Co-Tc element pair interact -22 meV. Interestingly, the element Ni shows the ferromagnetic order interaction with self-kind, but it interacts in an anti-ferromagnetic manner with other ferromagnetic dominant kinds, like Cr, V, and Mo.

It appears that the map in Fig. 22 (J_{ij}) and Fig. 23 (D_{ij}) have an equivalent pattern in terms of value strength. In this pattern the location of the four highly interactive zones at the four corners. Regarding these two figures (Fig. 22 and 23), SOC is the ultimate factor for anisotropic exchange interaction part D_{ij} while SOC influences the isotropic part J_{ij} very slightly [58]. Thus it is

almost impossible to find a strong and reliable relation between the J_{ij} and D_{ij} . However, we try to find a seeming interconnection between them.

It seems that the DMI between a couple of elements follows the strength of self-kind J_{ij} interactions (interactions among the same kind impurities in mono-doped calculations) of the associated elements that can be describe as follows:

- (i) strong self-kind J_{ij} - strong self-kind J_{ij} gives strong-DMI between the kinds of a couple.
- (ii) strong J_{ij} - weak self-kind J_{ij} gives mid-DMI interaction between the kinds of a couple.
- (iii) weak self-kind J_{ij} - weak self-kind J_{ij} gives weak-DMI interaction between the kinds of a couple.

Figure 24: The ratio from magnitude of DMI vector to the J_{ji} interaction with the same impurity arrangement as the arrangement for 20. The cut-off J_{ij} value is 1 meV and below this value we do not take the ratio DMI to J in consideration.

As the DMI and J_{ij} evolve non-collinear and collinear interactions respectively, we look at J_{ij} that dominates couple over DMI. Fig. 24 describes the dominance of J_{ij} magnitude over the magnitude of D_{ij} by calculating their ratio. Except for a few couples with the ratio (D_{ij}/J_{ij}) greater than one, for

instance, Cr-Fe, Mo-Tc, Mo-Ru, Co-Ni almost all couples are favored to the collinear interaction. Some interesting couples, for instances, V-V, V-Cr, Mo-Mo, Nb-Cr, Nb-V, V-Mo, Mn-Co, and Cr-Mo show higher J_{ij} compare to the D_{ij} which meets our expectation.

Regarding the observations (i) the DOS in the bulk region for individual elements (Fig. 18), (ii) the resultant magnetic moment (Fig. 20) from coupled impurities, (iii) the strength and order of Heisenberg exchange interaction J_{ij} (Fig. 22), (iv) the anisotropic exchange interaction D_{ij} (Fig. 23), and (v) the dominance of J_{ij} over the D_{ij} , we conjecture the elements V, Cr, Mn, Tc and Mo in the priority list for the next potential impurities. The elements from this list could be used as co-doping or mono-doping impurities for stable QAHE. We will progress our investigation on this narrow number of elements obtained from our observations.

7.5.3 Magnetic exchange interactions for different distances

In reality, a crystal does not consist of one or two unit cells rather is composed of a large number of unit cells. Moreover, the impurities are allowed to be doped in different neighboring unit cells at different distances. Regarding the magnetic interaction, the isotropic exchange interaction (J_{ij}) and the anisotropic anti-symmetric interaction (D_{ij}) compete with each other. So it is also a matter of concern whether at some distance D_{ij} defeats or J_{ij} . Or in another way the J_{ij} always shows supremacy over D_{ij} . In this section, we will only pay attention on some elements including V, Cr, Mn, Tc, and Mo found from the previous section. We endeavour to find probable candidates used in mono-doping or co-doping for the QAHE.

In Fig. 25 and Fig. 26, each sub-figure (e.g. Sub-Fig 25(a)) consists two sub-plots. The sub-plot with triangular points represents J_{ij} interaction in the same atomic layer (atomic layer corresponds to atoms $Bi1$) and the other sub-plot with circular points represents J_{ij} for impurities in different atomic layers (atomic layers corresponds $Bi1$ and $Bi2$). Other figures Fig. 27 and Fig. 28 stand for J_{ij} interaction in different distances (combination of the subplots discussed here) irrespective of atomic layers of the impurities.

For the impurities in the same atomic layer (Fig. 25 and Fig. 26), the J_{ij} values monotonically decrease with increasing the inter impurity distances. While the plot group (plot associated with the circular points) for interactions in the different atomic layers are somehow oscillatory. The reason behind this oscillatory pattern is RKKY indirect exchange interaction via intermediate electrons from the Te atomic layer. The RKKY indirect interaction comes from the contribution of impurities doped in different atomic layers.

Regarding the J_{ij} interaction analysis (in Fig. 27 and Fig. 28) the interesting couple are V-Cr, V-Mo, V-V, Cr-Cr, and Cr-Mo, more excitingly, V-Mo and Cr-Mo along with V-Cr²⁶.

²⁶Though V-Nb and Cr-Nb render strong ferromagnetic interaction but we are not considering the couples as the element Nb contribute larger density of states at the Fermi level

(a)

(b)

Figure 25: Magnetic interaction J_{ij} for impurities in the same as well as different atomic layers. The plot group corresponds to the impurities in different layers has been represented by circular points (impurities in the same atomic layer represented by triangular points) and shifted by 10 meV for lucid visibility.

(a)

(b)

Figure 26: Magnetic interaction J_{ij} for impurities in the same as well as different atomic layers. The plots are represented as described in Fig 25.

(a)

(b)

Figure 27: Magnetic interaction J_{ij} which is obtained from the combination of the different plot groups (in Fig 25 and Fig 26) associated with impurities located in the same atomic layer and in different atomic layers.

(a)

(b)

Figure 28: Magnetic interaction J_{ij} which are analogous to the plots in Fig 27 by replacing impurity-1 by Mn and Mo.

The Fig. 29 and Fig. 30 illustrate the anisotropic anti-symmetric interaction or Dzyaloshinskii–Moriya interaction (DMI) D_{ij} interaction in different inter-impurity distances. Regarding the absolute value of DMI represented by D_{ij} which is stronger for impurities doped in the same atomic layer compared to the impurities in the different atomic layers. For example, the D_{ij} interaction at distances 4.48Å and 8.77 Å give relatively higher interaction magnitude where the impurities are in the same *Bi* atomic layer. Some impurity couples e.g. *V – Tc*, *V – Nb*, *V – Cr*, *Cr – Mo*, *Mo – Tc* are considerably sensitive to the non-collinear interaction D_{ij} . On the other hand some other impurity couples, for instance *Mo – Nb*, *Mo – Mn*, *Mn – Cr*, have little D_{ij} part in their magnetic interaction part. It is an important fact to understand how stronger the D_{ij} is compared to the collinear interaction J_{ij} . Because, the DMI opposes collinear interaction and results the magnetic atoms alignment in right angle configuration which is the minimum energy configuration (see Eq. 50). The ratio between the corresponding quantities of the D_{ij} and the J_{ij} will give a good overview regarding there relative strength.

(a)

(b)

Figure 29: DMI interaction, D_{ij} which contains interactions between impurities in the same atomic layer as well as in the different atomic layers. The impurity arrangements are the same as described in a sub-figure of Fig. 25.

(a)

(b)

Figure 30: DMI interaction, D_{ij} which contains interactions between impurities in the same atomic layer as well as in the different atomic layers. The impurity arrangements are the same as described in a sub-figure of Fig. 26.

Fig. 31 and Fig. 32 describe the ratio between the magnitudes of D_{ij} and J_{ij} for different inter-impurity distance. The ratio set to zero if J_{ij} is less than the threshold value 1meV. The DMI interaction is highly sensitive at a distance 8.77Å while for other distances the ratio is smaller than one. However, for some impurity couples, for example, $V - Mn$, $V - Mo$, $V - Nb$, $V - V$, $Cr - Cr$, $Mn - Nb$, $Mn - Tc$, and $Mo - Nb$, the ratio value is lower than one, which is in agreement for developing QAHE. Regarding the double impurity calculations, a large contribution of the J_{ij} in the doped crystal comes from the impurities in the nearest unit cells. The ratio values of the couple below 2.0 can be considered as acceptable for stable J_{ij} . The couples (V-Cr, V-Mo, V-V, Cr-Cr, and Cr-Mo) obtained from the J_{ij} interaction analysis can be filtered and interesting couples are Cr-Cr, V-V, Cr-Mo and V-Mo. Thus for QAHE, the mixture of the different impurity kinds i.e. co-doping might give a good design of the magnetic structure.

The DMI interaction can not be described by a monotonic curve rather the interaction significantly rises at a certain distance. For further investigation of the ratio between DMI and isotropic Heisenberg interaction, this behavior necessitates to run multi-impurity (by a large number of impurities) calculations. A large number of impurities might decrease the ratio between the DMI and J_{ij} within the crystal. Because the DMI vector might come in different directions thus give small resultant DMI.

(a)

(b)

Figure 31: Comparative pictures between the DMI and J_{ji} by their ratio and the impurities are arranged as described in Fig. 27. The competition are taken into account if the J_{ij} has minimum value 1meV otherwise set to zero.

(a)

(b)

Figure 32: Comparative pictures between the DMI and J_{ji} by their ratio as presented in Fig. 31 but with different impurity-1 (Mn and Mo).

7.6 Magnetic Interaction Analysis With CPA Calculation

A different scheme to calculate the J_{ij} interaction among the impurities is the KKR-GF-CPA. In this scheme, the CPA medium of the disordered system is the weighted average of the mediums corresponding to the components (defects and host atoms) [58]. Thus it implies that the method can not give better results in the local position of the disorder than the KKR-GF impurity scheme. At a large distance, we can conjecture the equivalence of results from KKR-GF-CPA as the results from KKR-GF impurity scheme.

As a typical application of the KKR-GF-CPA method, we added some specific d-block elements(V, Cr, Mn, Mo) with a certain concentration, $x_{conc} = 0.05$, on atomic layers *Bi1* and *Bi2* of unit cell each.

As we have seen from the combine-impurity calculation, the elements V and Cr give stronger ferromagnetic interaction in mono-doped calculations as well as in co-doping dimer calculation(see Fig. 33). This is also experimentally established [9]. The element Mo shows strong J_{ij} in co-doping with V and Cr but weak J_{ij} in mono-doping calculation. Regarding these three elements, the results from the KKR-GF-CPA method show equivalent characteristics as that from the KKR-GF impurity scheme.

The method KKR-GF-CPA shows significantly different results for some impurity couples than the KKR-GF-impurity method. For instance, the J_{ij} orders for Mn-Mn and Mo-Mo are almost neutral (neither FM nor AFM) and AFM in mono-doped CPA calculation respectively, which disagree the results from KKR-GF-impurity calculations.

We also observe RKKY or indirect exchange interaction (discussed in chapter-4) for J_{ij} interaction in the CPA medium. In general, the interaction implies exponential type decays of J_{ij} rather than decreasing smoothly. Thus, the interaction strength between two atoms converges to zero with increasing distance.

Figure 33: Heisenberg Magnetic interactions J_{ij} between different atoms in different distances and in different atomic layers $Bi1$ and $Bi2$. Each sub-figure stands for J_{ij} (in meV) interaction with one specific element (from V, Cr, Mn, Mo) to the all of V, Cr, Mn, Mo. The asterisk data points stands for interactions between defects in the same Bi layer and the square graph points indicate interaction between the impurities in different Bi layers (the numbering of atomic layers has been discussed in Fig. 16).

Fig. 34 and Fig. 35 show the changes in ratio between D_{ji} and J_{ij} in different distances for different impurity defects. In this ratio measurement, we set the threshold J_{ij} to 1meV and the ratio values corresponding to the $J_{ij} \leq 1$ have been removed from the plot. Compare to the KKR-impurity calculations, the D_{ij} is weaker than collinear interaction J_{ij} at all distances. The behavior for weaker DMI is expected as the resultant DMI is the summation of DMI from different directions from impurities in different locations. Thus, the KKR-GF-CPA method suggests to pursue KKR-GF impurity calculation with co-doping as well as larger number of impurities in TIs. This approach will better understanding of the resultant J_{ij} and DMI.

Regarding the data analysis from KKR-GF-CPA calculations the impurity elements V, Cr, Mo and Mn, we can hypothesize that Mo is a highly potential element for stable QAHE along with V and Cr. Co-doping is also a possible approach for long perpetuity of collinear magnetic interaction with suitable impurity arrangement.

(a)

(b)

Figure 34: Comparative pictures between the DMI and J_{ji} (in meV) from KKR-GF-CPA method. The plots describe the ratio in the same atomic layer (by asterisk points) as well as in the different atomic layers (by square points) with impurity arrangement as described in Fig. 33.

(a)

(b)

Figure 35: Analogous plot as described Fig. 31 with different impurities.

8 Supervised Learning of J_{ij}

The performance of a specific task can be optimized using compatible machine learning algorithms [94]. In general machine learning algorithms can be categorized into three different groups, namely, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning [35]. In supervised learning, the approach is to construct a function or map which connects the input features of a labeled datum to its output or target. After analysing the labeled data set (training data set) with a compatible supervised learning algorithm, the model can predict the unknown output or the label of a new datum or data set associated with the same system. The unsupervised learning algorithm analyse the unlabeled data set and find the pattern among the data. The process separates the data into groups of the same properties. Finally, reinforcement learning does not need any labeled input and outputs, rather deals with the problems of finding optimal and sufficiently acceptable actions for a situation in order to maximize the gain. In material physics, the supervised learning is a widely exploited form of machine learning [35].

In our endeavour using the machine learning approach, we will try to predict the isotropic part, J_{ij} , of the exchange interaction of impurity pairs and compare it with the calculated value. For this purpose, we will conduct supervised learning using scikit-learn [95] python library on 2000 labeled J_{ij} data where the data are obtained for four different distances and different impurity combinations. The target J_{ij} is described by the descriptors

- (i) **r** (inter distance between the impurities),
- (ii) **grp0** (periodic table group of the first impurity),
- (iii) **ped0** (periodic table period of the first impurity),
- (iv) **en0** (Allen electronegativity of the first impurity),
- (v) **grp1** (group for the second impurity),
- (vi) **ped1** (period of the second impurity),
- (vii) **en1** (Allen electronegativity of the second impurity),
- (viii) **de1_en** (Allen electronegativity difference of the two impurities),
- (ix) **OS_d0** (number of odd or unpaired spins in d-orbital obtained from tabulated electronic configuration of the first impurity),
- (x) **OS_d1** (number of odd or unpaired spins in d-orbital obtained from tabulated electronic configuration of the second impurity),
- (xi) **OS_s0** (number of odd or unpaired spins in s-orbital obtained from tabulated electronic configuration of the first impurity),
- (xii) **OS_s1** (number of odd or unpaired spins in s-orbital obtained from tabulated electronic configuration of the second impurity),

- (xiii) `OS_0` (total number of odd or unpaired spins from the sum of `OS_d0` and `OS_s0` of the first impurity),
- (xiv) `OS_1` (total number of odd or unpaired spins from the sum of `OS_d1` and `OS_s1` of the second impurity).

To describe the electronegativity we have chosen the Allen scale which we have verified that it gives better results than the Pauling scale.

The impurities are embedded in the same Bi layer (*Bi1*) at 4.38Å (impurities in two nearest cells) and 7.51Å (impurities in two cells next to the nearest cells) and in the different layers (*Bi1* and *Bi2*) 6.1Å (impurities in two nearest cells) and 10.473Å (impurities in two cells next of the nearest cells).

8.1 Regression of J_{ij}

Regression is a fundamental algebraic as well as a statistical tool used in supervised machine learning. With this approach one can understand a dependent property of a system from one or more independent properties of the system. It explains how the changes of the independent variable (properties) manipulate the dependent variables (properties).

To evaluate the regression models' accuracy we will use a score of R^2 (also called *the coefficient of determination* or *R squared*)

$$R^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{\sum_i (y_i - y_{i,pred})^2}{\sum_j (y_j - \bar{y})^2} \right) \quad (55)$$

where y_i , $y_{i,pred}$, \bar{y} are the target value, predicted value and average of the target value, and root mean square error (*RMSE*). The R^2 unveils variation of the dependent variable due to the independent variables. The best possible score of the R^2 is 1 saying the outputs can be explained by well fitted curve. And the worst score is '0' which says the output feature is independent of the input features.

8.1.1 Linear regression

One fundamentally used regression algorithm is linear regression. Let us consider a physical property, $y^{(i)}$ of a physical system depends on other d physical properties, $x_1^{(i)}$, $x_2^{(i)}$, ..., $x_d^{(i)}$, where the superscript i indicates i^{th} datum of the data set. The property $y^{(i)}$ is called target or dependent variable and the $x_d^{(i)}$ is called feature or independent variable or descriptor. In linear regression, it is assumed that $y^{(i)}$ are linearly dependent on the features as

$$\begin{aligned} h_{\omega}^{(i)}(\vec{x}) &= \omega_0 + x_1^{(i)}\omega_1 + x_2^{(i)}\omega_2 + \dots + x_d^{(i)}\omega_d \\ &= \vec{\omega}^T \cdot \vec{x}^{(i)} \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

where the vector \vec{x} is (d+1) dimensional and the term associated with 1 is called intercept term. The vector $\vec{\omega}$ is called weight vector. The describe the importance of the features and the unit term can be assumed as the system constant which does not depend on the individual property. For a training data set of n labeled data, we can write a compact form

$$\vec{h}_\omega = \underline{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} \quad (57)$$

In the training period, the algorithm needs to be trained for reasonable $\vec{\omega}$ (including ω_0) which gives $h_\omega(\vec{x}^i)$ approach to the y^i . To formalise that, we will define a function called cost function. The cost function is intended towards zero,

$$J(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i^n (h_\omega(\vec{x}^i) - y^i)^2$$

This type of cost function is called least-square cost function²⁷.

Figure 36: Linear Regression Model with 1600 training data set and 400 test data set: The model's R^2 score is 0.074 and error RMSE is 3.215 on test data group.

The linear regression (LR) approach on 1600 J_{ji} training data set (Fig. 36), implies that J_{ij} data is not linearly dependent on our chosen descriptors. The value of R^2 for the LR model, 0.074, infers the output is mostly independent of

²⁷As the work mainly is not machine learning approach we will not discuss regression or any algorithm elaborately here. So we are discussing regression in a very little extend.

the descriptors. However, the *RMSE* (3.215) is smaller than we expect because a large number of data clusters locates around the zero J_{ij} and the target line pass through it.

8.1.2 Kernel Ridge regression

Kernel trick is often applied to ridge regression called Kernel Ridge regression (KRR), when a complex regression problem can not be used with simple linear regression model [35]. The word kernel has several meanings²⁸ and one approach is to create a third variable space from the other two variable spaces by kernel function. One common kernel function is

$$K_G(X_1, X_2) = \exp\left\{-\frac{|X_1 - X_2|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right\}$$

where σ is the characteristic length scale. Instead of the original features, the data are converted to the high-dimensional feature space $\theta(x)$. The new space is defined by the inner product $\langle \theta(x), \theta(y) \rangle$ and results in a non-linear regression in the original feature space. After error minimization by the cost function, this regression is generally referred to as kernel ridge regression (KRR).

Figure 37: Kernel Ridge Regression on 1600 training data set and 400 test data set: The model's R^2 score is 0.614 and error RMSE is 2.076 on test data group.

²⁸A deep discussion about the kernel functions and their meaning have been discussed in "Machine Learning: A Probabilistic Perspective" Murphy, K. P. - chapter 14.4.3, pp. 492-493, The MIT Press, 2012.

Applying linear, rbf (radial basis function), polynomial and sigmoid algorithms, with small regularization value 0.1 the KRR of 4-degree polynomial algorithm provides better prediction. Considerably larger discrepancy on the test data set visualise for $J_{ij} = 0$. But with this model the descriptors can be referred to describe the J_{ij} .

8.1.3 Decision trees regression

Unlike linear regression, Decision Tree Regression is a non-parametric algorithm. The algorithm mainly split the data set into small data subsets or regions on each step by applying if-else logic at each feature (Fig. 38). Each subset predicts an average output or fits a simple prediction model from the training data subsets. Thus, the unknown labeled datum corresponding to a subset predicts output that is the mean of the outputs of labeled data from the training set.

Figure 38: Typical Algorithmic flowchart for Decision Tree model: Features $x^{(d)}$ are split by a threshold value m_d . The final subsets are called leaves and the splitting point between two branches or sub trees is called internal node.

The Decision Tree regression (DTR) model and DTR by AdaBoost [96] are comparatively more suitable for our problem. The model DTR is eligible to predict J_{ij} with good accuracy (for larger values of J_{ij}) of test data set (Fig. 39) by giving RMSE 1.859. But, considerably the lower values of J_{ji} for the DTR model shows inconsistency between the predicted and target data. One possible reason is the relation between the output J_{ij} and the input features. The relation between the target J_{ij} and the input features can not be define linearly.

Other possible reason could be lack of certain feature which is responsible for lower J_{ij} . The value of R^2 (0.691) infers that the model also effectively has established the involvement of features with J_{ij} . The effort to further improve the DTR by AdaBoost ensemble methods was not successful. Because the boosting attempt increases the R_2 (after boosting 0.829) parameter and decreases RMSE (after boosting 1.38). Surprisingly, the boosting over the DTR model improves the feature involvement to the J_{ij} symmetrically i.e. the features from both impurities are equally responsible to the J_{ij} . For example, in AdaBoost with DTR the importance of group feature labels is more reasonable than DTR alone. Because the difference between the importance of group labels for two impurities is smaller in the combined model AdaBoost with DTR.

Figure 39: Decision Tree regression and boosting it with AdaBoost: For test data group R^2 for DTR is 0.691, and RMSE is 1.859, and with boosting DTR the R^2 0.829 and RMSE 1.382. For training AdaBoost with DTR the $R^2=1.0$ and RMSE=0.00.

From the sight of physics, the inter-impurity distance, group labels of impurities, d-orbital unpaired electrons and electronegativity should be important in determining J_{ij} and the importances of these are also in harmony with our feature importance bar graph (Fig. 40). Here, we used the Allen unit of electronegativity which has been defined from the average energy of the valence electrons in a free atom.

Figure 40: Relative Feature importance of DTR and it's boosting with AdaBoost.

9 Conclusion and Outlook

9.1 Conclusion

Our work is mainly constructed for the high-throughput investigations of magnetic interactions among magnetic elements, embedded in a topological insulator, by ab initio simulations (with KKR-GF method) as well as for a brief machine learning approach using the large dataset that is generated in this thesis. Where the magnetic impurities from the 3d and 4d elements are embedded in the TI Bi_2Te_3 by substituting positional host atoms Bi. The state of art of the magnetic impurities in TI Bi_2Te_3 is the QAH state, for instance, independently V-doped [10] and Cr-doped [11] $(\text{Bi}, \text{Sb})_2\text{Te}_3$ systems exhibit QAH effect but at very low temperature ($< 100\text{mK}$). The ultimate purpose of this work is to explore other or better magnetic impurities, along with V and Cr to be used in mono-doped or co-doped materials, giving long lasting QAH states from bulk TI especially QSHI. Therefore the work necessitates to discussion about (i) novel properties of matter like QHE, QSHE as well as QAHE that exist in TI, (ii) concrete theoretical concepts of the KKR Green function method behind the simulation calculations, (iii) Heisenberg model for magnetic interactions among the atoms (here we only have concentrated on the magnetic impurity atoms) in crystal, (iv) rigorous analysis of the Heisenberg parameters from the impurity calculations and (v) development of an inevitable workflow *combineimps_wc* of AiiDA-KKR package [97] (vi) finally data manipulation tools from supervised machine learning for predicting the magnetic interactions. Later, to compare the data obtained from KKR-GF-impurity method, we have also collected the impurity interaction data on some specific elements using another well known method called KKR-GF-CPA. As the work is integrated with a large number of ab initio calculations, we have also discussed the advantages of one of the modern simulation automation software AiiDA which supports in running a huge number of calculations and preserving the calculation data in securely and easily accessible database. With the help of the AiiDA, we have extended our pre-existed AiiDA-KKR plugin compatible with multi-impurity calculations.

In chapter-2, we recalled the theory of topological band structure, as an exotic state of matter appeared in topological insulators, which describes the topological states and the topologically invariant numbers.

The Korringa-Kohn-Rostoker Green function (KKR GF) method discussed in chapter-3 has been used for the first principles calculations of this thesis which is particularly well suited to study impurities embedded into crystalline solids. Without any scrutiny description of mathematical calculation and proof, we have tried to establish the concept behind the construction of Green function for perfectly ordered crystal and impurity and finally the algorithm behind the development of *KKRimp* code of *JuKKR* code package. Next comes chapter-4, in which we have demonstrated different parts of the magnetic interactions and their relative strength. As in previous chapter, without any description of mathematical calculation, we introduce the method of infinitesimal rotations for calculating the magnetic interactions between the magnetic impurities.

The following chapter-5 & the chapter-6 consist of the basic construction of AiiDA infrastructure and the development of the AiiDA-KKR plugins. One of the pivotal parts of this work is to extend the *AiiDA-KKR plugins* by integrating workflows (the band structure workflow *kk_r_bs_wc* and the multi-impurity workflow *combineimps_wc*). In this work, both of the developed workflows have been used successfully, especially the multiple impurity workflow, *combineimps_wc*, which is in the core application for this high-throughput investigations. The *combineimps_wc* is also successfully tested for more than two impurities.

Chapter-7 discusses core investigation associated with the shingle impurity and dimer impurity calculations run for the thesis work. The Total number of the calculations is 2100 which consists of 20 DOS calculations for single impurity doped TI, 20 single impurity calculations (using *kk_r_imp_wc* single impurity workflow) and 2060 dimer calculations (using *combineimps_wc* multi-impurity workflow). Though each of the single impurity as well as dimer calculations has a lot of numerical data related to the calculations, here mainly we have extracted the magnetic moments of the impurity atoms and exchange interactions (for dimer calculations) that include isotropic interaction J_{ij} and anisotropic anti-symmetric interaction (DMI) D_{ij} .

In chapter-7, as a part of the analysis for potential magnetic impurities, we started the investigation from density of states (DOS) calculation of single impurity doped TI and continued via total magnetic moment from dimer calculations. It is important that at the Fermi level the DOS contribution from the impurity atoms should be small to protect the band structure properties of the host crystal (almost zero DOS at the Fermi level). By setting the threshold DOS 2.6 states/eV slightly above the DOS for V and Cr, each transition elements of Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, Y, Zr, Mo, Tc, Ru, Rh, Ag and Cd contributes equal or lower DOS with respect to the threshold value. Another desired property of the impurities is strong magnetic moments. Regarding the dimer impurity calculations, the total magnetic moment from the impurities is not exactly algebraic sum of the individual magnetic moments, but it slightly changes due to charge sharing between the impurity atoms. With the threshold value $4\mu_B$ (each magnetic element must contribute at least $2\mu_B$) for total magnetic moment and considering the elements obtained from DOS analysis, we speculated that the elements Mn, Mo, V, Co, Tc and Cr might be interesting for potential impurities.

From the analysis of dimer calculations in chapter-7, we have found that the J_{ij} interactions from the KKR-GF-impurity calculations show monotonically decreasing interaction behavior with increasing inter-impurity distances for the impurity couples embedded in the same Bi atomic layer of Bi_2Te_3 crystal. Interestingly, the J_{ij} interactions between the impurities of a couple do not show the monotonic behavior rather oscillatory when the two impurities are embedded in two nearest Bi atomic layers. The oscillatory behavior of J_{ij} comes from the RKKY indirect exchange interactions between the impurities via secondary interaction with the inter-impurity atomic layer of Te. Both the J_{ji} and the D_{ij} are stronger for impurities in the same atomic layer compare to that for impurities in different atomic layers. More importantly, DMI dominates the J_{ij} magnetic interaction at a certain distance of 8.77\AA except for a few com-

binations. Regarding the impurities Mn, Mo, V, Co, Tc and Cr, the impurity couples giving overall higher J_{ij} and at the same time lower D_{ij} (ratio < 1) are V-V, Cr-Cr, V-Cr, V-Mo, and Cr-Mo, and more importantly V-Cr, V-Mo and Cr-Mo. As the impurity couples satisfy one of the prerequisites (the larger and stable J_{ij}) for stable QAHE, thus co-doping with these impurity elements would be good approach. In comparison with the KKR-GF impurity calculation, the KKR-GF-CPA method also suggests the impurity elements V, Cr, Mo and Mn for potential elements for doped TIs, from which we can hypothesize that Mo is a highly potential element for stable QAHE along with V and Cr. Therefore, it can be speculated that moderated codoping with V, Cr and Mo might give access to the stable and strong J_{ij} as well as QAH state.

A related work by Peixoto et al [98], the local magnetic and electronic configurations for impurities V and Cr (with concentration $V_{0.1}(Bi_{0.32}Sb_{0.68})_{1.9}Te_3$) in $(Bi, Sb)_2Te_3$ have been discussed with photoemission, X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) and density function theory. With the help of XMCD spectra analysis, under small applied magnetic field of 0.01T, it has confirmed stability of ferromagnetic interaction and sizeable magnetic moments ($m_s = 2.33\mu_B$ for V and $m_s = 3.32\mu_B$ for Cr) from the 3d-states of V and Cr impurities doped in $(Bi, Sb)_2Te_3$. From this thesis with the first principle calculations, the magnetic moments for V ($m_s = 2.65\mu_B$) and Cr ($m_s = 3.80\mu_B$) from the single impurity calculation (Fig 54) are comparable to the magnetic moments from the XMCD spectra analysis [98]. The differences in magnetic moment from the two work could be reduced if the KKR-GF impurity calculations (from this work) are run with same impurity concentration or with multiple impurities. Also using KKR-GF method, the density of states (DOS) of impurities from the impurity calculation has also been successfully explained by the experimental results obtained from resonant photoelectron spectroscopy (resPES)[98]. Which successfully analogies the location of the DOS of impurities and the shift of DOS around the Fermi level due to the different charge doping.

Finally, in chapter-8 we have implemented supervised machine learning tools, especially regression models, on the collected J_{ji} from 2060 dimer calculations. We found that Linear Regression does not work and we need at least the kernel trick (KRR) or even better a decision tree. The models are well fitted for the higher value of J_{ij} but give lower performance for lower J_{ji} interaction values. As expected the features e.g. inter distances between the impurities of dimer calculations, group number of the impurity are important.

9.2 Outlook

As is mentioned, the stable but larger J_{ij} is a prerequisite for stable QAHE. For some couples of impurities with larger J_{ij} , the impurity couples also see larger DMI interaction which is not welcomed at all. Thus, this work demands further analysis for impurity calculations with more than two impurities potentially with the larger number of impurities. As with the larger number of impurities the resulting DMI vectors might come in different directions which might turn the resultant DMI to a smaller and more stable state.

Though the QAHI is already established with the V and Cr doped Bi_2Te_3 but with very low temperature ($< 100\text{mK}$). Our investigation suggests that co-doping with (Cr,V), (Cr,Mo) and (V,Mo) would give more stable ferromagnetic order. To understand the stability of magnetic design in QSHI, the calculation of Curie temperature plays an important role and the temperature can be calculated from the Heisenberg interaction parameters. The higher Curie temperature refers to the more stable magnetic order until that temperature. Thus calculating the Curie temperature from a larger impurity doped crystal would give the plenitude for this high-throughput impurity calculations.

Machine learning tools will accelerate the research looking for a stable magnetic design for stable QAHE in higher a temperature. With proper machine learning areas, e.g. Deep Learning (DL) and Reinforcement Learning (RL), and a sufficient amount of data from the impurity calculations (e.g. features of impurities and crystals) one will be able to predict other possible magnetic design even in other host crystal without running computationally expensive multi-impurity calculations. Thus this work can be further improved by machine learning tools.

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